

Programmable materials: Current trends, challenges, and perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Research into programmable materials has attracted extraordinary interest since the nineties, when the term “programmable” was introduced for the first time. In its widest definition, the term is used to denote materials that are designed to be highly dynamic, either in shape and/or physical/functional properties, on-demand and in a precise, sequential predetermined way. Such unique feature allows them to adapt to various needs and offers new opportunities in several application fields, enabling them to overcome the limitations of traditional materials. The present paper aims to introduce readers to the world of programmable materials, enhance their interest, knowledge, and skills in the field, and provide useful insights and new ideas on how to approach their development and implementation. Accordingly, this paper offers an overview and discussion of current state-of-the-art and recent progress up to future perspectives. First, the historical evolution and definition of these materials as well as the types of programmable properties achievable are presented. Then, the different programming strategies that could be used to tune material properties are covered, with an emphasis on the constituent materials, applied stimuli, and geometrical arrangements. Finally, real-world applications, ongoing challenges, and future directions for this exciting class of materials are discussed.

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1. Introduction

Throughout history, the discovery of materials has always driven important social and technological advancements. As proof of this relationship, several historical periods, such as the Copper Age and the Iron Age, are named after the materials discovered and used at those times.

However, materials were generally considered passive and static. Consequently, an object made of a certain material usually had a unique form and function and could not change to perform multiple tasks depending on the need.

Therefore, over the past three decades, the scientific community has worked intensively to seek answers to the following question: *Can we create a material that can be programmed to perform multiple tasks?*

The noticeable advancements in a variety of fields, including materials science, computer-assisted design, and additive manufacturing, have helped the community in answering such a question, giving rise to a real “material revolution” leading to the establishment of the so-called class of *programmable materials* [1].

The term “programmable matter” was first introduced by Toffoli and Margolus in 1991 [2]. Inspired by the cellular automata machine CAM-8, the authors defined programmable matter as a three-dimensional uniformly textured, fine-grained computing medium that can be assembled into lumps of arbitrary size, dynamically reconfigured, interactively driven, and accessible to real-time monitoring, analysis, and adjustments. In the same year, Knudsen et al. [3] used the term “self-programmable matter” to define a dynamic system made of functional interacting elements that can develop new functionally-active elements through autonomous (self) dynamics. Starting from their first discussion in 1998, McCarthy and Snyder [4] patented a programmable dopant fiber composed of quantum structures formed on a fiber-shaped substrate. The fiber may find application, e.g., as a programmable dopant that can be inserted in bulk materials and can be controlled by external signals. Later, Goldstein et al. [5,6] investigated hardware and software necessary to produce programmable matter that can arrange itself in order to match the visual appearance of an object. Zykov and coauthors [7] developed new machines acting as autonomous modular robots capable of physical self-transformation. The latter was possible using a set of cubes powered through the base-plate and transferring power and information through their faces. Trogemann and Vierhoff [8] defined a machine as programmable if its behavior can be changed without re-configuring its inner structure. Therefore, they viewed the behavior as inherent to the machine itself and, consequently, considered programming as the ability to trigger, combine, and manipulate that behavior. Then, research on programmable materials was accelerated in 2007, when the U.S. Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) funded a project [9] aiming at designing and manufacturing micro-scale robotics systems that could morph into larger military systems. Shape-shifting robots, named “milli-moteins”

(i.e., mechanical proteins), were designed and constructed at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT). In 2010 Hawkes et al. [10] defined programmable matter as a material whose properties can be programmed to achieve specific shape or stiffness changes upon command. In the same year, the term was also influenced by the emergence of new manufacturing technologies such as 4D printing [11]. The latter refers to an emerging trend in the field of stimuli-responsive materials, which uses additive manufacturing to create structures with complex geometries. These structures are capable of evolving in shape and function over time—considered the fourth dimension—under the influence of external stimuli, after their production. Tibbitts first introduced the term “4D printing” during his 2013 TEDx talk and applied this technology to the construction of programmable machines [12]. According to Tibbitts and colleagues [13,14], the concept of programmable materials refers to a self-assembly process that enables structures to autonomously change their shape and/or functional properties, eliminating the need for human intervention or robotic mechanisms such as motors, wires, and electronics. Based on this definition, they identify two forms of programmable matter: (1) self-transforming structures made of 4D printed pre-connected elements; (2) unconnected voxels that can autonomously come together or break apart to form structures. In particular, in form (1) the term “4D printing” was often used by Tibbitts and colleagues to denote programmable matter. In 2016, Andreoletti and Rzezonka [15] proposed replacing the term “programmable” with “processual” to shift the emphasis to the materials’ capacity for change and to their temporal characteristics. The authors argue that “programmable” suggests a prescriptive code applied to passive matter, whereas “processual” portrays material as engaged in an ongoing interplay of active elements, implying a collaborative interaction among objects, humans, and their surroundings. More recently, Takeuchi and coauthors [16] explained that the definition of programmable materials, intended as artificially-designed systems in terms of their physical shapes or functions in response to external stimuli, encompasses a wide range of systems and scales, including designed molecules, functional polymers, machines, and architectures.

As it can be understood from the reviewed literature, the definition of programmable materials has changed along the years, inspired first by hardware architectures and computer programming and then influenced by complex living and chemical systems and new technologies. Specifically, the term “programmable materials” was extended to include any medium that could be programmed to change its physical properties and used interchangeably with “programmable matter”, although a discussion regarding their meaning and differences between the two terms can be found in the literature. In particular, Berwind et al. [17] made a distinction between materials and matter, stating that the properties of a material are the result of an aggregation of matter that, when it accumulates to a certain volume, demonstrates properties that are statistically significant and consistent upon additional scaling; hence, matter is the fundamental building block of materials.

Moreover, thanks to the advancements in several material and manufacturing technologies as well as application fields at various

Fig. 1. Numbers of results along the years, found in the Web of Science, searching for “programmable materials” or “programmable matter” (update: July 2024). Only articles, reviews, early access, book chapters, and proceedings have been considered in the record count.

scales, research on programmable matter has increased along the years and today it finds application in various disciplines, including physics (e.g., crystals, complex fluids), chemistry (e.g., shape-changing molecules), bioengineering (e.g., DNA self-assembly, cell engineering), and robotics (e.g., modular and nano-scale robotics). Fig. 1 shows the numbers of results found in the Web of Science, after searching for “programmable materials” or “programmable matter”. It is clear that the number of research contributions is still steadily increasing, although first reports have been published more than 30 years ago.

The opportunity of changing the properties of a material in a programmable manner allows to solve many of the complications encountered with traditional materials, e.g., limited performed tasks, high costs, difficult manufacturing, difficulties in meeting specific requirements, or limited adaptation to the environment. This has a great potential in impacting both the research and the industrial field, opening unique opportunities for various sectors requiring high adaptability and cost savings coupled with multi-dimensional changes, such as solar energy systems, electronics, packaging, medical devices, transportation, robots, and actuators. However, significant efforts have been primarily focused on the research aspect rather than on the market and industrial side. In fact, the commercial application and the industrial production of these materials is still marginal. Market analyses suggest that the global market of programmable materials is expected to growth with a significant compounded average growth rate (CAGR) between 2021 and 2029, pushed by the rapid advancements in nano- and 4D printing technology [18]. Product types will regard carbon fibers, textiles, and wood, while applications will cover the construction, healthcare, military/defense, automotive, and textile field. At the same time, the still high cost of 4D printers will be the major challenge affecting the market growth. The North America market is predicted to grow at the highest CAGR thanks to the 4D printing technology, since it is mostly concentrated in the United States.

Motivated by the potential of these materials, the present paper aims to introduce readers to the world of programmable materials, enhance their interest, knowledge, and skills in the field, and give useful insights and new ideas on how to approach their development and implementation to potentially promote commercial applications and market growth.

Accordingly, this paper offers an up-to-date overview on programmable materials and of their properties, also discussing current challenges and future advancements. Particularly, the strategies that could be used to program material properties will be covered, with an emphasis on the constituent materials, applied stimuli, and geometrical

arrangements. Then, we will discuss how the different types of programmable properties can be exploited in real-world applications. The discussion will give important insights on the numerous opportunities that remain to be addressed towards final technology exploitation.

To the best of author’s knowledge, only a limited number of review papers on programmable materials are available and they focus on specific classes (e.g., stimuli-responsive polymers [19], shape memory polymers [19], shape-programmable polymers [20], mechanically-active hydrogel-based materials [21], hydrogels [22], liquid crystal elastomers [23], liquid matter [24], architected materials [25], mechanical [26] and acoustic [27] metamaterials), aspects (e.g., constitutive modeling [20], fabrication methods [20,21], shape-programming [28–30], stiffness-programming [31]), and application fields (e.g., therapeutic agent delivery systems [19], photonics [32]) of programmable materials. Many programmable properties, such as color, adhesion, damping, still need to be analyzed and discussed in detail to exploit their full potential.

Finally, it is worth noting that, in this paper, based on the literature reviewed, we do not differentiate between materials and matter and instead embrace a broad definition of programmable materials. Henceforth, the term “programmable” will denote materials engineered to be highly dynamic, either in shape and/or in physical/functional properties such as color, stiffness, density, and damping capacity, which can be altered on-demand -either autonomously or through user inputs- and in a precise, pre-established sequence post-fabrication. For this reason, the term “programmable” will be used interchangeably with “tunable”. We note that, in this context, we will restrict our attention only on materials capable of multi-step changes (for instance, evolving from an initial to a final target state, passing through intermediate target states, as schematically shown in Fig. 2).

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly presents the different types of programmable properties that have been obtained in the current literature. Then, Section 3 discusses how these properties can be programmed, while Section 4 shows how they have been used in various application fields. Conclusions, challenges, and perspectives will be finally given in Section 5.

2. Classification of programmable properties

Programming the behavior of a material refers to the possibility of featuring the material with one or more properties that can be adapted to different situations, needs, or environmental changes or to achieve specific functions that would be unachievable with fixed ones. Particularly, programmable behavior may manifest itself under different types of shape’s and/or physical/functional properties’ changes.

Here, we briefly define and discuss the types of programmable properties achieved in the current state-of-the-art and their potential applications.

2.1. Shape

Shape is a physical property of materials, that allow to describe them in terms of a geometrical body.

Nam and Pei [33] proposed a taxonomy to classify the different types of shape changes allowed and schematically represented them as illustrated in Fig. 3. As it can be observed, both basic and complex shape-changing modes can be identified. The former are single-step deformations; the second ones are multi-step deformations and can be seen as an extension of the basic modes. Combination of basic and complex modes is also possible. In particular, complex or combined basic-complex shape changes involving two or more steps of deformation are those permitting to achieve a programmable behavior.

Typically, shape-programming (also denoted as shape-reconfigurability) is the main area of interest for researchers [30]. Intuitively, the most advantageous programmable shape changes from a practical point of view are those ensuring transformations from

Fig. 2. Simple example of programmable material, according to the definition and focus adopted in the present review.

Fig. 3. Matrix of shape-changing behaviors and type of deformations. Source: Adapted with permission from [33] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

the two-dimensional to the three-dimensional space. In fact, programming an initially flat (i.e., two-dimensional) structure that undergoes three-dimensional shape transformations upon the application of a stimulus brings several advantages, including an easy and cheap fabrication of components as well as an efficient stacking for storage, transport, and deployment [28,34]. Particularly, autonomous (self) shape-programming becomes relevant at very small/large scales or for remote applications [11,34,35]. For instance, it overcomes the difficulties associated to the delicate operations needed to accurately execute microscale fabrication processes; it avoids external operations that increase the complexity and risk of failure in space structures or that are impractical or prohibitive for underwater robotics or for the deployment of medical devices.

Moreover, shape-programming is often used to indirectly tune other material properties as those described in next sections.

2.2. Stiffness

Stiffness is the extent to which a material resists deformation in response to an applied force.

Stiffness modulation becomes fundamental for various applications, including personalized devices (e.g., rehabilitation components), actuators, and robots. As an example, the possibility of controlling the flexibility of robots is important for maximizing the efficiency during locomotion or other movements, as demonstrated by numerous animals, insects, or invertebrates in nature [36]. Also, in-vitro models with tunable stiffness allow to better mimic the in-vivo changes of the extracellular matrix and to test their effect on cellular response and/or treatment conditions [37]. Programming material stiffness is also attracting for controlled drug release rates.

2.3. Poisson's ratio

The Poisson's ratio describes the relative amount a given material contracts (expands) transversally when axially stretched (compressed) and typically ranges from -1.0 to $+0.5$ for isotropic linear elastic materials. This value can indeed be higher for materials with different structural properties, such as orthotropic or anisotropic materials, or in the case of two-dimensional structures; see [38] and references therein.

Materials that possess a negative Poisson's ratio are generally referred to as auxetics.

The demand for tuning the Poisson's ratio is expected to rise due to the increasing need for high-precision equipment with the appropriate stability to withstand mechanical disturbances [39]. Also, it is crucial for improving energy absorption performances of personalized objects for comfort and protection purposes, as in gears for sports or helmets [38]. In tissue engineering applications, scaffolds having a tunable hybrid (i.e., both negative and positive) Poisson's ratio may better mimic the elastic behavior of native tissues [40].

2.4. Adhesion and friction

Friction is the resistance to motion when two bodies or surfaces in contact slide on one another, while adhesion is the ability of two bodies or surfaces to hold together. Adhesion and friction between surfaces depend on a suite of mechanical and geometrical parameters, including the roughness and mechanical properties of surfaces [41].

Controlling and tuning adhesion and friction are essential in many biomedical and industrial applications, e.g., in the field of mechanical engineering, tribology, soft robotics, and drug delivery, to increase the efficiency and/or working life of components [42,43]. In fact, as an example, they ensure featuring robots with maneuvers and locomotion capabilities that can be adapted to different environments and interacting surfaces.

2.5. Structural damping and energy absorption

Structural damping and energy absorption refer to the ability of a system to lose vibration energy and to absorb mechanical energy, respectively.

Systems that rely on the inherent damping properties of their constituent materials, such as viscoelastic behaviors or plastic deformations, do not permit the engineering of products that simultaneously resist and adapt to extreme environmental conditions, dissipate or absorb a significant amount of energy, and have a reversible behavior. High-tech, automotive, and aerospace industries could instead benefit from tunable properties, e.g., for morphing and vibrational isolation applications. Controlling the attenuation of mechanical vibrations is also essential to prevent the premature failure of civil structures and infrastructures or to ensure human safety in products like crash bumpers and helmets, as well as in environments with operating machinery and engines where vibrations are prevalent [44,45]. Similarly, the ever-increasing demand for enhanced and adaptable energy absorption to protect against impact accidents requires the design and development of structures with tunable superior energy-absorbing capabilities under extreme loading conditions [46].

2.6. Thermal properties

The coefficient of thermal expansion and thermal conductivity are the most common thermal properties that researchers aim to tune. The former measures the change in a material's dimensions upon temperature changes, while the latter is a measure of its ability to conduct heat.

The tunability of the thermal expansion coefficient is crucial for various applications such as construction, aerospace, fuel cells, and electronics. This is because discrepancies in the thermal expansion coefficients of different materials can result in substantial thermal stresses, potentially leading to decreased reliability or fractures. Moreover, components like bearing, precision structures and airplane components benefit from materials with a stable area/volume despite temperature fluctuations. Other applications, such as piping connections and dental fillings, necessitate materials that align with the thermal expansion of their surrounding environment [47,48].

Similarly, modulating the thermal conductivity can lead to a precise control of the heat flow. This is vital for addressing key challenges in energy conversion systems, information processing, and electronic thermal management. An effective thermal management is crucial for improving the performance, reliability, and comfort in applications like artificial skins and wearable electronic devices [49].

2.7. Electrical properties

Electrical conductivity, defined as the capacity of the material to carry an electrical current, is the electrical property most frequently tuned according to the current literature. Another property is the dielectric constant which is a measure of the amount of electric potential energy, in the form of induced polarization, that is stored in a given volume of material under the action of an electric field.

Materials with adaptable electrical conductivity show promising applications in electronic switches, optoelectronics, conformal electronic devices, adsorptive sensing, random access memory, and reconfigurable electronics and sensors (see [50] and references therein). Tuning of the dielectric constant has great potential in applications such as tunable oscillators, phase shifters, and varactors [51].

2.8. Acoustic properties

Acoustic properties are those that govern how materials respond to sound waves and are thus concerned with the transmittance of sound, including propagation, absorption, and scattering.

Tuning sound transmittance has been a long-standing goal across various fields, such as in the development of acoustic lenses, cloaks, and absorbers for applications in marine biology, medical imaging, underwater communication and sonars [52]. Further, tunable and broad bandwidth sound-eliminating capacities are necessary for noise reduction purposes in many engineering applications [53]. Moreover, conventional materials like metals, polymers, ceramics, and wood are commonly used across different media (solids, liquids, and gases) and frequency ranges, but they cannot significantly alter their acoustic properties after production [54]. The mismatch of acoustic impedance between these materials and their surrounding media results in energy loss and pulse aliasing, thus presenting a significant challenge to acoustic imaging and communication. Overcoming this challenge necessitates the use of programmable materials that can adjust their acoustic impedance to suit various surrounding media and operational frequencies. Moreover, manipulating sound and elastic waves may lead to materials exhibiting tunable properties not found in naturally-occurring materials, such as tunable negative refraction, acoustic cloaking, and acoustic subwavelength imaging.

2.9. Electromagnetic properties

Electromagnetic properties govern the rate at which a material responds to absorption or emission of electromagnetic radiations (e.g., radio waves, micro waves, ultraviolet rays, infrared rays, and visible light rays).

As for acoustic properties, programming the transmittance of electromagnetic waves is possible. This includes controlling how an incident electromagnetic wave interacts with the material and translates into the capability to determine whether the wave is transmitted, reflected, or absorbed. Moreover, manipulating electromagnetic waves may also lead to materials exhibiting tunable properties not found in naturally-occurring materials, such as tunable negative dielectric permittivity, negative index of refraction, or negative magnetic permeability. Response to light as well as programmable optical properties will be discussed in detail in the next section.

Manipulation of electromagnetic waves plays a crucial role across various application fields such as communication, imaging, holography, spectroscopy, and sensing systems [55,56]. Materials designed to shield

against electromagnetic interference are essential for the reliable functioning of electronics and spacecraft in the harsh conditions of space. Furthermore, the absorption of electromagnetic waves has emerged as a significant area of research. This is driven by the growing concern over electromagnetic pollution, which poses a threat to the uninterrupted performance of electronic devices.

2.10. Optical properties

Optical properties of a material, as light refraction, light reflection, light scattering, light absorption, and birefringence, are defined as its interaction with electro-magnetic radiation in the visible.

A large array of applications ranging from optical coatings, meta-surfaces, imaging, and plasmonic antennas to biosensors and photo-detectors would greatly benefit from the tuning of optical properties [32]. Light manipulation could be used to create light detection and ranging (i.e., lidar) sensors, accelerate brain scanners, or cause a response in other properties, like conductivity. Color-programming leads to important applications in anti-counterfeiting technology, smart sensors, multi-spectral camouflage, dynamic displays and textiles, and biomedical components [57,58].

2.11. Motion

Motion is the act or process of changing the physical position.

Programming the motion of a material makes it capable to move intelligently and directionally in order and is specifically relevant for liquid matter in microfluidic systems and for smart robots. Particularly, tuning the wettability of surfaces is an efficient solution to indirectly manipulate the pinning and sliding of droplets. Moreover, programming the structure of coatings can be applied for varying surfaces' wettability and ensuring better control of flows [24]. Programming motion is also very advantageous in robotic systems to efficiently move through obstacles towards the desired location [59]. In such a case, the motion of robots is often controlled indirectly via shape changes [60].

3. Programming strategies

Various strategies have been proposed to program the material properties discussed in Section 2. They rely on three main approaches: (i) inherent properties of the constituent material(s); (ii) applied stimulus; (iii) geometrical arrangements. Fig. 4 reports the basic approaches available from the current literature for each strategy listed. These approaches can either be combined or considered separately.

In the following sections, we review these approaches, together with their advantages and disadvantages. We underline that, for approach (i), we focus on the macroscopic properties and behavior of these materials and not on the chemical aspects of the constituent materials. However, related references on the subject will be provided to complete the discussion. Moreover, several techniques, including electrospinning, molding, and additive manufacturing, are employed to fabricate programmable materials. However, a review of all these techniques is out of the present scope. On this specific topic, we suggest the reader to refer to review papers as [20,21,25,28].

3.1. Constituent material(s)

Programmability can be achieved thanks to the inherent behavior of the constituent material(s) (see the first box in Fig. 4). Particularly, programmable behavior is generally associated to the responsiveness of these materials to stimuli such as thermal variations, magnetic or electric fields, and pH, as detailed below. Non-responsive materials may be also used, but in this case programmability is achieved by applying other types of external inputs, such as mechanical loads, and/or by designing specific geometrical arrangements. Such cases are addressed in Sections 3.2 and 3.3, respectively.

As schematically represented in the first box in Fig. 4, programmable materials can be composed of one or more constituent materials. Particularly, single material-based structures typically show simple and limited programmable behaviors. To achieve more complex behaviors, material gradients or multi-material approaches are thus employed.

In the following, we examine all these approaches, as outlined in the first box of Fig. 4. For each approach, we detail the programmable properties achieved, according to the definition given in Section 2.

3.1.1. Single material

Programmable materials may consist solely of a single constituent material, the stimuli-responsive nature of which can be harnessed to attain programmability.

Stimuli-responsive materials undergo alterations in their physical properties in response to changes in their surrounding environment. These environmental changes can be physical (triggered, e.g., by variations in temperature, light, electrical signals, or magnetic fields) or chemical (induced, e.g., by shifts in pH, moisture, or redox conditions). The interested reader can refer to review papers on stimuli-responsive materials [156,157] for details.

To date, both natural and synthetic materials have been used, together with a broad range of possible stimuli. Material response to such stimuli can be either irreversible or reversible. Table 1 summarizes the most used materials, together with their advantages and disadvantages, while Table 2 contains some examples of works achieving the programmable properties discussed in Section 2 through the use of the materials listed in Table 1.

Thermo-responsive materials. The most commonly studied materials are thermo-responsive materials that change their properties depending on temperature variations. The stimulus in question operates through heat transfer or mass transport within a medium, typically resulting in a slow, transport-controlled actuation speed that is challenging to control locally. It is possible for the stimulus to be controlled remotely, without direct contact.

Shape memory materials, including polymers, alloys, and ceramics, are among the most commonly used types of thermo-responsive materials for shape-programming. These materials are able to recover the permanent (processed) shape from a temporary (deformed) shape after the application of a proper stimulus. Such an ability is known as thermal shape memory effect when the recovery is triggered by heating. Particularly, the shape memory effect in polymers and hydrogels can be classified into three main categories, based on the number of temporary shapes that can be fixed through the so-called programming step: (i) one-way, in case of one temporary shape; (ii) multiple, in case of two or more temporary shapes; (iii) two-way, in case of a reversible transition between two temporary shapes. Superelastic effect, which allows the material to recover the shape upon removal of the mechanical load, can also be observed in shape memory alloys. The reader is referred to review papers for details about the chemistry and physics of shape memory materials [158,159], alloys [160], polymers [161–164], and hydrogels [91].

Materials displaying the multiple shape memory effect are the most interesting shape-programmable materials, since they ensure a sequential transition from two or more temporary shapes, up to the recovery of the permanent one. These include, e.g., polymers exhibiting triple and quadruple shape memory effect through the incorporation of two or more well-separated transition temperatures [68,69], polymers exhibiting the so-called temperature-memory effect (TME) through a broad transition temperature range [61–63], and hydrogels with triple shape memory effect [64]. Specifically, within the context of the TME, the recovery process of the permanent shape from its temporary states is initiated at distinct temperatures. These temperatures correspond to those used during the programming step of the material and are commonly referred to as “deformation temperatures”. As an example, Inverardi et al. [61] demonstrated the potential of the TME in designing

Fig. 4. Basic approaches employed in the current literature to program material properties.

Table 1

Stimuli-responsive materials used in the current state-of-the-art to achieve programmable behavior. *compared to other chemical stimuli.

Stimulus	Pros.	Cons.
Thermal	Contact-free control	Generally slow response Difficult local control Unsuitable for volatile droplets
Light	Contact-free control Local control Precise control Generally fast response	Difficulty in moving highly viscous droplets Suitable for relatively transparent media
Magnetic	Contact-free control Generally fast response Small-scale actuation	Difficult local control Suitable for certain liquids
Electrical	Generally fast response Precise control Local control	Non contact-free control Difficult local control
Ultrasound	Contact-free control Local control Efficient energy transmission Strong penetration Biocompatibility	Ultrasound-responsive cores consume space Potential damage to tissues
Mechanical	No energy consumption	Non contact-free control
pH	Adapt and react to physiological pH variations	Non contact-free control Difficult local control Generally slow actuation
Redox	Adapt and react to physiological redox variations	Non contact-free control Difficult local control Generally slow response
Moisture	Large volume changes Fast response*	Non contact-free control Difficult local control Difficult control of expansion direction
Solvent	Large volume changes	Non contact-free control Difficult local control Difficult control of expansion direction
Ions	Adapt and react to physiological ionic environments	Non contact-free control Difficult local control Generally slow response
Biomolecules	Suitable for biomedical applications	Non contact-free control Difficult local control Generally slow response Generally irreversible response

Table 2
Examples of programmable properties achieved using stimuli-responsive materials (cont.).

Programmable property	Stimulus	Examples
Shape	Thermal	[61–72]
Shape	Light	[64,73–76]
Shape	Magnetic	[77–79] & refs therein
Shape	Electrical	[70,80,81] & refs therein
Shape	Ultrasound	[82–84] & refs therein
Shape	Mechanical	[85]
Shape	pH	[86] & refs therein
Shape	Redox	[87]
Shape	Moisture	[88]
Shape	Solvent	[89,90] & refs therein
Shape	Ions	[90,91] & refs therein
Shape	Biomolecules	[21,70] & refs therein
Shape	Thermal-light	[92]
Shape	Thermal-magnetic	[93]
Shape	Thermal-pH	[94]
Shape	Thermal-ion	[95]
Shape	Thermal-ion-solvent	[96,97]
Shape	Thermal-ion-redox	[98]
Shape	Thermal-light-ion	[99]
Shape	Light-magnetic	[100]
Shape	Light-humidity	[101]
Shape	Light-electrical	[102] & refs therein
Stiffness	Thermal	[72]
Stiffness	Light	[103]
Stiffness	Magnetic	[104]
Stiffness	Electrical	[31,105] & refs therein
Stiffness	Ultrasound	[83] & refs therein
Stiffness	Mechanical (solid)	[85]
Stiffness	pH	[106–108] & refs therein
Stiffness	Redox	[109]
Stiffness	Moisture	[110]
Stiffness	Solvent	[107] & refs therein
Stiffness	Biomolecules	[111] & refs therein
Stiffness	Electrical-mechanical	[112]
Stiffness	Thermal-humidity	[110]
Poisson's ratio	Thermal	[113]
Poisson's ratio	pH	[114]
Adhesion & friction	Thermal	[115,116] & refs therein
Adhesion & friction	Light	[116] & refs therein
Adhesion & friction	Magnetic	[117]
Adhesion & friction	Electrical	[43,116] & refs therein
Adhesion & friction	pH	[116] & refs therein
Adhesion & friction	Redox	[116] & refs therein
Adhesion & friction	Solvent	[116] & refs therein
Adhesion & friction	Ions	[116] & refs therein
Adhesion & friction	Biomolecules	[118]
Damping	Thermal	[119]
Damping	Magnetic	[45,120] & refs therein
Damping	Electrical	[105] & refs therein
Thermal expansion coefficient	Thermal	[121] & refs therein
Thermal expansion coefficient	Light	[121,122] & refs therein
Electrical conductivity	Thermal	[71,123]
Dielectric constant	Electrical	[51,124]
Electrical resistance	Mechanical	[125]
Electrical conductivity	pH	[126]
Electrical conductivity	Thermal-mechanical	[127]
Electrical conductivity	Electrical-mechanical	[112]
Acoustic	Thermal	[128]
Acoustic	Light	[129,130]
Acoustic	Magnetic	[39]
Acoustic	Electrical	[131]
Acoustic	Ultrasound	[83] & refs therein
Electromagnetic	Magnetic	[132]
Electromagnetic	Thermal-strain	[127]

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued).

Programmable property	Stimulus	Examples
Optical	Thermal	[133]
Optical	Light	[134–137] & refs therein
Optical	Magnetic	[138,139] & refs therein
Optical	Electrical	[81,140]
Optical	Ultrasound	[83,141] & refs therein
Optical	Mechanical	[142,143]
Optical	pH	[144,145] & refs therein
Optical	Moisture	[32,145] & refs therein
Optical	Solvent	[91] & refs therein
Optical	Ions	[145] & refs therein
Optical	Biomolecules	[146]
Optical	Light-DNA	[57]
Optical	Thermal-light-mechanical	[147]
Motion	Thermal	[24,60,148] & refs therein
Motion	Light	[24,149] & refs therein
Motion	Magnetic	[24,150,151] & refs therein
Motion	Electrical	[24,70,152,153] & refs therein
Motion	Acoustic	[24,154,155] & refs therein

a 4D printed self-locking clamp (see Fig. 5A). The clamp was subjected to a two-step programming at two different deformation temperatures (T_{high} and T_{low}) to fix two temporary shapes; then, the isothermal recovery was studied by immersion of the structure in a water bath. As it can be seen, the recovery includes two separate motions at different time instants, allowing the end-tab to enter in the hole before rotating to ensure the locking feature. The TME offers several benefits, including the ease of managing the shape recovery through mechanical programming rather than altering the chemical composition of the polymer. Additionally, it allows for the attainment of multiple shape transformations when the programming involves a series of steps, each conducted at a specific temperature.

To address the irreversible nature of the TME and of the multiple shape memory effect in general, a range of solution strategies has been proposed to ensure reversible shape-programming.

A typical solution is to exploit the two-way shape memory effect in liquid crystalline elastomers and multi-phase semi-crystalline networks. Liquid crystal elastomers combine liquid crystal order and elastomeric properties in aligned, loosely crosslinked polymer networks and can undergo reversible deformations in response to external stimuli [23, 65]. As an example, Guo et al. [65] obtained liquid crystal elastomers that underwent shape re-programming via the shape memory effect and the subsequent reversible actuation of the programmed shape through temperature variations and photo-thermal heating. Dual-phase liquid crystal elastomers networks with a crystalline melting transition above a liquid crystalline transition, that could be re-programmed in a timescale of seconds, were proposed in [67]. Multi-phase semi-crystalline networks include all crosslinked systems with two or more crystalline domains or a single crystalline phase with a wide melting range [162]. Particularly, the two-way shape memory effect can be achieved by leveraging on the synergistic interaction between the crystalline and amorphous phases present within the network itself. As an example, the presence of two crystalline phases ensures the sequential and reversible switching between two or more temporary shapes [72].

Other solutions applied modifications to the chemistry of the studied systems to ensure re-programmable behavior. As an example, Wu et al. [66] proposed a poly(acrylic acid) (PAA) hydrogel, prepared in the presence of diethylenetriamine (DETA), subsequently treated by calcium acetate ($\text{Ca}(\text{Ac})_2$), with remodelable permanent shape and capable of programmable cold-induced shape recovery. The charge-assisted hydrogen bonding between PAA and DETA imparted the hydrogel with re-modelability, while the heat-induced hydrophobic aggregation of polymer chains and acetate groups resulted in shape fixation and recovery by heating and cooling, respectively. Programmable devices were obtained through assembling of hydrogel blocks with different concentrations of $\text{Ca}(\text{Ac})_2$.

Incorporating droplets or liquids (i.e., substances that are liquid at room temperature) that react to temperature changes into polymer

matrices as functional additives allows for shaping the so-obtained composite materials into specific configurations (see [24,71] and references therein). Liu et al. [71] created conductive fibers with a liquid metal filler gradient dispersed in a polymer matrix. The fibers demonstrated thermally-programmable shapes depending on the heat absorbed by the liquid metals and electrical conductivities. Upon heating, the fibers showed a transition from an insulator to a conductor with programmed conductivity along the axial direction. Both the shape programmability and conductivity transition were highly reversible through thermal cycling. It is noted that approaches involving thermal stimulation are often inappropriate for volatile droplets due to the risk of sample evaporation or compromised accuracy in measurements [24].

Apart from shape-programming, thanks to material's responsiveness to thermal changes, other properties can be tuned over temperature ranges. Examples include the programming of the stiffness [72], Poisson's ratio [113], and thermal [121] and electrical [123] properties. Jin et al. [113] studied the temperature-dependent Poisson's ratio behavior of polyvinyl alcohol-based poly n-isopropyl acrylamide (PVA-PNIPAm) hydrogels and alginate hydrogels through compression tests. Fig. 6A presents the obtained results in terms of normalized Poisson's ratio versus temperature.

One-way shape memory polymers were also used to tune friction in [115]. The authors exploited a cycloaliphatic polyether urethane block copolymer distributed as Tecoflex EG-72D (Lubrizol Corp., USA) to develop surfaces able to switch from a flattened to a micro-fibril structured topography with nano-scale steps upon heating. Thus, the shape changes of the surface induce variations of its frictional properties from nearly isotropic to anisotropic along the fibril direction. Since the frictional anisotropy increases linearly with the step height, it can be also controlled by interrupting the recovery process at any intermediate step height. Thanks to the frictional changes, the surface allows to transport microparticles through small random vibrations.

Pseudoelastic shape memory alloy springs were proposed to develop tunable friction pendulum isolation systems to regulate vibrations in structures subjected to near-fault seismic activity in [119]. Specifically, the continuous changing of the temperature of the SMA spring during mechanical loading–unloading (pseudoelastic) cycles induced by an earthquake alters its energy dissipation. This affects and improves the control efficiency of the entire isolation system compared to conventional systems.

Temperature-responsive materials have been also used to manufacture photonic and phononic structures whose properties can be programmed and controlled through shape changes induced by temperature variations [128,133].

Moreover, programmable shape changes induced by shape memory behaviors are often used to program the motion of smart machines and systems. In particular, two commercial one-way shape memory

Fig. 5. Examples of materials and structures with programmable shape. (A) Double-programming and sequential closing of a clamp made of a shape memory polymer featuring the TME, though uniform heating in a water bath. Adapted with permission from [61], copyright 2019, John Wiley and Sons. (B) Re-programmable photo-chromism and photo-actuation of a 4D printed TiNC/LCE kirigami-inspired composite via local control of both light exposure and mesogen alignment. Adapted with permission from [75], copyright 2023, John Wiley and Sons. (C) Shape-change regulated by cell-driven contraction and viability of composite gels over time. Adapted with permission from [165], copyright 2019, John Wiley and Sons.

polymers, named VeroWhitePlus and FLX9895, were used to develop actuators that harnessed bistable elements sequentially, thus allowing the programmable motion of untethered, soft swimming robots [60].

In addition, manufacturing temperature-sensitive surfaces are established methods for altering the wettability of surfaces and thus controlling the motion of liquids (see [24,148] and references therein). Consequently, liquids can be systematically directed along predetermined

paths. Fig. 7A shows the drop sliding motion on different anisotropic slippery liquid-infused porous surfaces under heating and cooling cycles. The surfaces were prepared by using paraffin, a thermo-responsive phase-transition material, as a lubricating fluid and directional porous polystyrene films as the substrate.

It should be noted that thus far, our discussion has focused on materials activated by direct heating methods such as hot gas or

Fig. 6. Examples of materials with programmable Poisson's ratio. (A) Temperature-dependent compression test results of PVA-PNIPAm hydrogels and alginate hydrogels preformed in an environmentally-controlled chamber. Results are represented in terms of normalized temperature-dependent Poisson's ratio behavior. Adapted with permission from [113]. (B) Topology and shape optimized architectures for a programmable range of Poisson's ratio values under mechanical load. Adapted with permission from [166], copyright 2015, John Wiley and Sons. (C) Mechanical properties of a single building block. Kinematic paths are defined as angle relations during its reconfiguration in EC, EP, and LT paths. Theoretical and experimental Poisson's ratios and normalized stiffnesses of a module in EC, EP, and LT paths. Adapted with permission from [167], copyright 2021, John Wiley and Sons. (D) Poisson's ratio of the Miura-ori and Eggbox origami patterns varying the folding angle. Adapted with permission from [168], copyright 2022, Elsevier.

water. However, indirect heating methods –such as those utilizing light, electricity, magnetic fields, or ultrasound– have also been employed. These are explored below under the other classes of stimuli-responsive materials. In this scenario, the materials and related shape changes are intrinsically activated by heat, as various forms of energy are transformed into thermal energy via specific material components (e.g., fillers). Indirect heating offers numerous advantages over direct heating, as it encompasses the benefits associated with other types of stimuli.

Light-responsive materials. Light-responsive materials respond to light due to embedded nanoparticles or particular chemical compounds that interact with light; see review papers as [21,172,173] for details about the chemistry and physics behind. The light source can be a wavelength-specific laser or a (LED) lamp. Accordingly, various approaches exploit material responsivity to far red (FR), near-infrared

(NIR), infrared (IR), ultra-violet (UV), white, and visible (VIS) light through the inclusion of nanomaterials, chromophores, photosensitive molecules, or photocleavable crosslinkers; see [174] and references therein. The great advantage of this class of materials is the possibility of a non-invasive, precise, and local contact-free control of the stimulus along the structure and an overall fast response to the stimulus. A significant benefit of IR and NIR lights is their ability to permeate various materials (e.g., biological tissues), thereby expanding their potential applications. Nonetheless, the application of light control is contingent on the specific requirements of different droplets, substrate materials, and actuation mechanisms, which necessitate particular light wavelengths and precise angles of incidence. The effectiveness of light stimulation may be generally limited to media that are sufficiently transparent, as opaque substances can impede light penetration.

Fig. 7. Examples of materials with programmable motion. (A) Thermo-controllable drop sliding motion in the parallel direction of anisotropic slippery liquid-infused porous surfaces. The indicated substrate tilt angles of water, glycerol, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and ionic liquid droplets correspond to their critical sliding angles. Adapted with permission from [148], copyright 2018, American Chemical Society. (B) Reversible isotropic/anisotropic sliding conversion on a surface thanks to unpressed and pressed micropillars made of one-way shape memory polymers. The infusion with perfluoropolyethers allows to control both the cessation and initiation of motion. Adapted with permission from [169], copyright 2021, Elsevier. (C) Selective droplet transport within independent zones (Zone 1-shallow gradient, Zone 2-intermediate gradient, and Zone 3-steep gradient) under different levels of applied compressive strains. Adapted with permission from [170]. (D) Anisotropic wettability surface from ferrofluid assembled templates under highly inclining magnetic field, inspired by *Nepenthes alata* plant. Adapted with permission from [171], copyright 2017, John Wiley and Sons.

NIR light-responsive examples of materials for shape-programming exploit the triple shape memory effect of hydrogels incorporating ferrous oxide [64], the two-way shape memory effect of shape memory polyurethane composites doped with citric acid-modified Prussian blue nanoparticles [74], the reversible response and the motifs of the photomasks of liquid crystal elastomer composites consisting of up to 0.20 wt% poly(ethylene glycol)-modified gold nanorods [73], and the

reprogrammable and localized photo-chromism and photo-actuation of titanium-based nanocrystal/liquid crystal elastomer (TiNC/LCE) composite inks for 4D printing [75]. In this latter work, kirigami structures were actuated by changing the step length h via patterned UV irradiation and site-specific NIR laser irradiation (see Fig. 5B). Moreover, the authors were also able to exhibit reversible color-switching between white and black as well as controllable color patterns in response to

Fig. 8. Examples of materials with programmable stiffness. (A) Three-piece functionalization platform consisting of a SNAP-tag fusion protein (Opto-SNAP), benzylguanine maleimide, and a cysteine-containing polymer. The activation of Otoprotein-SNAP-tag fusion proteins (when attached to polymers through the aforementioned system) increases polymer-polymer interactions, thus stiffening the gel upon exposure to blue light and softening it in the dark. Adapted with permission from [103], copyright 2021, American Chemical Society. (B) Force–displacement curves under uniaxial compression of origami-like unit cells at different configurations (indicated as “States #”) under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Adapted with permission from [175]. (C) Biomimetic continuum robot constructed by tensegrity. Reused with permission from [36], copyright 2023, John Wiley and Sons.

UV irradiation and oxygen exposure of the TiNC/LCE composite ink. Montesino et al. [76] presented an ink containing a green-absorbing perylene diimide chromophore, to prepare light-active liquid crystalline elastomer actuators via direct ink writing. Green light irradiation ensured photo-thermal actuation, but also new absorption bands in the FR and NIR, ascribed to the formation of radical species. FR irradiation resulted in mechanical actuation and in a recovery of the original absorption spectrum. This reversible transformation enabled spatial reconfigurability of the actuator’s response to FR light, ensuring complex deformation modes by simply exciting the element with homogeneous FR light, without the need for any structural modification of the actuator.

Moreover, light-responsive materials generally possess a stiffness that can be tuned over various orders of magnitude by the stimulus. As an example, Hopkins et al. [103] proposed a material (called OptoGel) that stiffens upon exposure to blue light and softens in the dark (see Fig. 8A).

Similar observations hold for the thermal expansion coefficient [121, 122]. Batti et al. [122] proposed a light-driven, highly oriented film based on ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMW-PE), containing a photo-responsive additive, 2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-ditertpentylphenol (BZT) (Fig. 9A). The material is able to absorb light thanks to BZT, converts energy into heat, and possesses high stiffness (about 80 GPa) and a negative thermal expansion (NTE) that can be tuned via draw ratio. Thanks to these features, the material exhibits a fast (< 1 s) and reversible photo-induced thermal response upon exposure to UV light, which results in high actuation stress (about 70 MPa) at a low strain ($< 0.1\%$).

Electrophorheological fluids whose rheological properties are reversibly tuned by both UV and VIS light and electric field [176] and spiropyran-functionalized upconversion nanoparticles for spatio-temporal and precise regulating of intracellular zinc by means of NIR light [177] were proposed.

Various light-responsive materials have been also used to manufacture photonic and phononic structures whose properties can be

programmed and controlled through shape changes induced by light irradiation [130,136,137]. Gliozzi et al. [129] printed a UV-curable resin containing methyl red as an azo-dopant, using a commercial digital light processing 3D printer, to manufacture elastic metamaterials with tunable width of a frequency band gap. Fig. 10A shows the experimental setup consisting of a piezo-actuator exciting elastic waves in the slab. A 405 nm laser beam was used to induce a spatially selective photo-softening effect depending on the illumination area and a 633 nm laser vibrometer (SLDV) scanned the whole structure while detecting point-by-point the out-of plane oscillation amplitude. Spectral response and measured dispersion curves are reported.

Color-programming was also proposed. Punpongsanon et al. [135] printed a voxel pattern, assigning a unique photo-chromic color to each voxel on the object’s surface. Subsequently, all voxels corresponding to colors not required for the intended appearance were selectively deactivated using VIS light, while those required for appearance were activated by UV light. Later, to overcome the limitations of this approach (e.g., low resolution, limited number of colors, need for a multi-material 3D printer), Jin et al. [134] used photo-chromic dyes mixed into a single solution to create re-programmable multi-color textures made from a single material. The dyes switched their appearance from transparent to colored when exposed to light of a certain wavelength. To this purpose, the authors used regular office projector’s red, green, and blue LEDs. The procedure was entirely reversible, allowing for the object to be recolored repeatedly according to user preference.

Finally, some studies have also performed the control of liquids’ motion via applied light stimuli by modifying the substrate surface; see [24] and references therein. As an example, Rao et al. [149] fabricated a silicon oil-infused porous slippery surface with UV-responsive controllable wettability. This surface was integrated with a non-UV-responsive slippery surface to form composite UV-responsive surfaces. By adjusting the design of the “cutting patterns” on the

Fig. 9. Examples of materials with programmable thermal properties. (A) Photo-actuation behavior of drawn UHMW-PE/BZT films upon UV exposure at a wavelength of 365 nm, leading to NTE that can be tuned via draw ratio. Adapted with permission from [122], copyright 2020, American Chemical Society. (B) Thermal tunability of a shape memory polymer metamaterial architecture. Adapted with permission from [178], copyright 2023, Elsevier. (C) Isotropic thermal deformation of 2D kirigami-like units. Each unit consists of 1/4 units with the same pattern (111, 110, 100, and 000). Adapted with permission from [179], copyright 2020, Elsevier. (D) Bioinspired programmable self-shape arrays. Adapted with permission from [180] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 10. Examples of materials with programmable acoustic properties. (A) Light-responsive metamaterial patterned with periodic square pillars, made of UV-curable resin containing methyl red as an azo-dopant. Adapted with permission from [129] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). (B) Phononic bandgap programming in kirigami by input sequencing. Adapted with permission from [181], copyright 2023, John Wiley and Sons. (C) Micro-slotted dielectric elastomer bending actuator (MSDEBA), inspired by flower petals responding to light or heat, responding to sound frequency variations and driven by high voltage. Adapted with permission from [182] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

non-UV-responsive surface and the pattern of the UV masks, the droplet-guiding channels could be programmed orderly.

Magneto-responsive materials. Magnetic-responsive materials respond to a magnetic field through different mechanisms [21]. They can be directly actuated by a magnetic field; in such a case, the stimulus induces a reorganization of the magnetic structures embedded within the material, resulting in topographical changes of the material and/or material property changes that revert the material back to its original state upon removal of the stimulus [20]. Alternatively, these materials can be also actuated indirectly by incorporating ferromagnetic structures within a thermo-responsive polymer matrix; in such a case, the magnetic field produces heat that triggers the thermal response of the matrix. For a detailed discussion on chemical aspects, the reader is referred to, e.g., [79,183]. Magnetic-responsive materials are advantageous for achieving complex shape changes at small scale (< 1 cm), ensuring fast responses and contact-free control. Further, the magnetic field can be specified not only in magnitude, but also in its direction [77].

Along this line, in [77], programmable shape alterations were realized through the integration of a passive element and an active element, the latter being responsive to magnetic stimulation. The active element comprised soft silicone rubber infused with fine neodymium-iron-boron particles. Conversely, the passive element consisted of the same silicone rubber matrix embedded with aluminum powder. By properly designing the distribution between the passive and active components it was possible to apply a magnetic field with a non uniform magnitude and orientation profile along the structure, thus determining programmable and controlled shape changes. Qi et al. [78] manufactured magnetic filaments made of polylactic acid (PLA) and carbonyl iron particles via extrusion-based 3D printing and embedded the manufactured elements in silicone rubber. Thanks to 3D printing, it was possible to manufacture magnetic structural elements with any shape, distribution, and orientation to generate anisotropic magnetization profiles leading to programmable shape changes.

Moreover, material stiffness [104] and electromagnetic properties [132] can be tuned over various orders of magnitude by the stimulus.

The wettability and adhesion properties of surfaces with magneto-rheological elastomer micropillars were investigated under different magnetic fields by Yang et al. [117]. Fig. 11A shows the fabrication procedure of these surfaces capable of reversible changing their wettability and adhesion properties by on/off switching of a magnetic field. Optical microscope images in Fig. 11A also show the stiffness tunability under a magnetic field, which can transform the micropillars from a water-adhesive to a water-repellent state.

Magneto-rheological materials (fluids in particular) may be programmed in vibration dissipation and damping [120] and to manufacture tuned liquid dampers in civil engineering structures [45]. Fig. 12A shows the different working types in which magnetic fields are applied on tuned sloshing and tuned liquid column dampers to control structure vibration subjected to dynamic loads.

Various stimuli-responsive materials have been also used to manufacture photonic and phononic structures whose properties can be programmed and controlled through shape changes induced by a magnetic field [39,139]. An interface modified with superparamagnetic colloidal nanocrystal clusters was proposed in [138], featuring gradual color changes from red to blue with an increase of the applied magnetic field.

Magnetic fields also serve as a powerful solution to remotely move and wirelessly program the motion of liquids, ensuring fast reactions. The creation of localized gradients of the magnetic field enhances precision in control and lays the basis for complex programming. Nevertheless, the application of magnets is limited to driving paramagnetic or ferromagnetic fluids, with antimagnetic liquids being the exception [24]. Direct manipulation involves rendering the liquid

Fig. 11. Examples of materials with programmable friction and adhesion. (A) Reversible switching of the wettability and adhesion properties of superhydrophobic surfaces made of magnetorheological elastomers by on/off switching of a magnetic field. Adapted with permission from [117], copyright 2018, American Chemical Society. (B) Kirigami-inspired adhesives consisting of alternating stiff and compliant regions under 90° peel loading. Adapted with permission from [184], copyright 2018, American Chemical Society.

(e.g., oil, water, liquid metal) magnetic by incorporating magnetic particles (e.g., steel bead, iron, Fe_3O_4 , ferronickel) or by electrochemical reactions to coat liquid metal surfaces with a layer of magnetic material (e.g., nickel, CoNiMnP), resulting in the so-called magnetic fluids; see [24] and references therein. As an example, Kim et al. [150] proposed a gallium-based liquid metal droplet coated with ferromagnetic materials. The approach based on direct manipulation alters the liquid's inherent properties, and strong magnetic fields risk dislodging the magnetic components from the liquid, thereby compromising its structural integrity and magnetic properties. In scenarios where high purity is paramount, such as in biochemical analyses, the direct addition of ferromagnetic particles to the liquid could lead to contamination [24]. An alternative strategy involves the indirect control of the liquid motion, exerted by magnetic materials positioned adjacent to the liquid itself [151]. In such a case, shape changes of surfaces are indirectly used to program the movement of liquids.

Electro-responsive materials. Electro-responsive materials respond to an electric field and are composed of conductive polymers or matrices embedded with conductive elements [20,21]. The reader is referred to, e.g., [186,187] for a detailed discussion on the chemical aspects. Electrically-induced stimuli offer the advantage of seamless integration with the electrical sensing, control, and power systems that are prevalent in autonomous machines and robotics. Furthermore, electrical impulses can be precisely and rapidly propagated through a material [31].

The paper by Bai et al. [80] introduces a shape-programmable metasurface composed of an array of filamentary metal traces. This configuration is actuated by reprogrammable, distributed Lorentz forces,

which arise from electrical currents flowing in the presence of a static magnetic field. Specifically, the possibility of independent voltages defines the distribution of current density in the conductive surface and therefore the control of the Lorentz forces, allowing the programming of shape changes. A programmable responsive polymer coating over a pattern of counter electrodes that can be activated selectively to achieve localized and structured wrinkling deformation was developed in [81]. A multi-state light reflection–diffusion–grating device for smart optics was then presented.

Moreover, electro-responsive materials generally possess a stiffness (see, e.g., [31,105] and references therein) or electrical properties (e.g., [51,112,124]) that can be tuned over various orders of magnitude by the stimulus. Electrorheological fluids and elastomers that possess reversibly tunable characteristics (including stiffness, damping, and rheological properties), fast response, and low energy consumption are discussed in [105]. Ferroelectric materials have spontaneous polarization which can be reversibility switched by an external applied electric field. One important feature of these materials is that their dielectric constant varies as a function of direct current electric field. Thus, they are promising candidates for applications requiring high dielectric tunability, low dielectric loss tangent, and appropriate level of dielectric constant. For a detailed discussion the reader is referred to, e.g., [51,124].

Programmable adhesion and friction has been achieved in [43] using ionic liquid-mixtures. Programmable adhesion and friction in electro-active mechanically-active hydrogel-based materials have been proposed; see [116] and references therein. In particular, two types of electrical stimuli are usually considered in mechanically-active

Fig. 12. Examples of materials and structures with programmable structural damping and energy adsorption. (A) Tuned sloshing and tuned liquid column dampers including magnetic fields applied with different directions, made of magneto-rheological materials. Reused with permission from [45] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). (B) Schematic of the different regimes that can be programmed in a metamaterial based on unit cells with two functional layers under mechanical loading. Adapted with permission from [185].

hydrogel-based materials, i.e. static or redox-based [21]. Static-type materials are activated by the formation of osmotic gradients upon exposure to a static electric field. Conversely, redox-based materials contain a redox-active group within their matrix that undergoes an electrochemical reaction when subjected to an applied electric field. The static mechanism offers the benefit of remotely-controlled actuation. However, it is less convenient compared to other remote actuation methods due to the necessity for salts in the solution. The redox-type mechanism is distinct from chemically-triggered redox-responsive materials, as it relies on electrical current to provide the electrons needed for reduction, rather than chemical reactions.

Various materials, including piezoelectric ceramics [188], have been also used to manufacture photonic and phononic structures whose properties can be programmed and controlled through shape changes induced by electrical voltage [131].

Zhang et al. [140] developed a color-programmable device by sandwiching an elastic light-emitting tube with two aligned carbon nanotube sheets. The device is capable of emitting light when subjected to an alternating electrical field. Moreover, a multi-color capability was realized by incorporating various color light-emitting tubes within a single inner electrode. The emitted light's color and intensity can be modulated independently of the observation angle.

Programmable motion has been achieved in electro-responsive hydrogels [70,152] as well as in liquid metals (see [24,153] and references therein).

Ultrasound-responsive materials. Ultrasound-responsive materials have capabilities enabled by different ultrasound-induced effects (namely, cavitation, microstreaming, structural vibrations, acoustic scattering, and acoustic radiation force) or indirectly induced by heating. For a detail discussion on chemical aspects and performances the reader can refer to, e.g., [189,190]. Ultrasound offers numerous

benefits: it transmits energy efficiently and safely through complex and opaque media; its effects can be precisely targeted to specific areas, both spatially and temporally; its frequency can be adjusted across a vast range—over twelve orders of magnitude—to effectively couple with phenomena and objects at different time and length scales. Moreover, ultrasound, especially high-intensity focused ultrasound, stands out as an advantageous external stimulus for medical applications, owing to its non-invasive nature, accessibility, cost-effectiveness, absence of ionizing radiation residues, tunable spatio-temporal control, and broad patient acceptability [84,191]. In fact, for clinical acceptance, remote heating must be precisely targeted to prevent hyperthermic damage to adjacent tissues. High-intensity focused ultrasound enables the precise concentration of ultrasound energy on in-vivo targets, ensuring efficient heating with minimal energy loss in the surrounding tissues [192]. As a proof of this, shape memory polyurethane ureas were remotely and precisely triggered with magnetic resonance guided high-intensity focused ultrasound in [192].

The use of ultrasound-responsive materials for achieving programmable responses is still limited, but deserves investigation. Examples where ultrasound has been used to control the propagation of light, the propagation of sound, and the mechanical properties of soft materials as well as where ultrasound-induced effects have been combined with other physical, chemical, and biological systems are discussed in [83,84]. A semi-interpenetrating polymer network-based hydrogels with multiple functions (swellability in water, sensitivity to low frequency ultrasound, shape programmability, and shape memory induced by ultrasonic cavitation-based mechanical forces) was proposed in [82]. A hydrogel based on N-isopropylacrylamide and N,N'-methylenebisacrylamide (MBAm) was demonstrated to change its optical transparency reversibly in response to temperature changes induced by on-off ultrasound heating in [141]. This in turn led to an alternation in the microstructure of the hydrogel. Accordingly, the

material was used to develop a tunable drug delivery platform for the triggered release of two large molecules (bovine serum albumin and dextran). In fact, their release amount increased with increasing temperature, and the application of ultrasound further increased the release. Finally, acoustic waves can be also harnessed to control liquid droplets; see [24] and references therein. As an example, Jeon et al. [154] developed an oxidized liquid metal droplet-based energy harvester that converts acoustic energy into electrical energy by modulating an electrical double layer that originates from the deformation of the oxidized liquid metal droplet. Surface acoustic waves are especially effective for capturing and manipulating minute liquid volumes, as demonstrated in [155] by proposing surface acoustic wave-based acoustic tweezers.

Mechano-responsive materials. In addition to these classical physical stimuli, mechano-responsive materials have been also utilized. These materials react to mechanical forces, resulting in alterations to their properties. A discussion on chemical aspects is available in [193–195].

As an example, Zhang et al. [85] designed a mechano-controlled biocatalytic system at the molecular level, which is incorporated into hydrogels to regulate their mechanical properties on a material scale. Under cyclic tensile-loading, hydrogels exhibited self-stiffening or self-softening properties, while bilayer hydrogels exhibited tailored shape-morphing behavior under mechanical stimulation.

Triboelectric hydrogels are also of great interest for mechanical force sensing and energy conversion. As an example, He et al. [125] generated hydrogels that detect a wide range of strains (tensile: 2%–600%; compression: 0.5–119.4 kPa) and respond by changing their electrical resistance as well as output voltage signal (see Fig. 13A). These hydrogels are based on polyacrylamide (PAM), silk fibroin (SF), graphene oxide (GO), and poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):poly(4-styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS). PAM has good biocompatibility and tunable elasticity, but poor mechanical properties. Thus, it is combined with SF that, as a natural protein, has excellent biocompatibility, remarkable mechanical toughness, mechanical strength, and low-cost features. Then, GO and PEDOT:PSS are mixed into the PAM/SF hydrogel to further enhance its conductivity. Despite their sensitivity, these triboelectric materials can indicate the magnitude of an applied force, but they generally lack the capability to provide spatial information about the point of application of the force. However, advancements in the field have been proposed to address this limitation, as discussed in [196].

Photonic crystal hydrogels inherently react to mechanical forces via their crystal constant - a parameter linked to the periodic structures' dimensions and spacing within the material. Tuning this constant enables the generation of structural colors that fall within the VIS light range, thereby facilitating the detection of even minimal forces applied to the hydrogel. A demonstration of the fast response of photonic hydrogels as pressure-actuated full-color displays is reported in [142] (Fig. 14A). Mechano-responsive light scatterers based on a strain-driven reconfiguration of the surface or internal structure have also emerged, featuring fast responses, a simple composition/fabrication, and no energy consumption [143].

Chemo-responsive materials. Chemo-responsive materials are a class of materials that respond to various chemical inputs, thereby altering their physical and chemical properties [21]. pH responsivity, for instance, may be controlled by acidic or basic motifs, such as carboxylic or amine groups. Redox (oxidation–reduction reaction) responsivity can be triggered by either reducing/oxidizing reagents or, alternatively, using an external electric field (as discussed above). Moisture responsivity can be activated by a change in humidity, due to the presence of hydrophilic groups in the material. A well known class of moisture-sensitive materials are hydrogels, which are water-swollen polymers that alter their volume upon a change in humidity. Ion-responsive materials can be achieved by changing the ionic composition and ionic strength of their environment. Biomolecule-responsive materials are

properly included in the class of biochemical-responsive materials since they generate a mechanical response to a variety of molecules, such as glucose, protein, enzymes, and nucleic acid sequence (DNA), due to the incorporation of specific molecular moieties. The interested reader may refer to, e.g., [203] for details on the chemistry of these systems. These materials, together with their programmed response, are of great interest, particularly in the areas of diagnostics, tissue engineering, and drug delivery.

Within the class of chemo-responsive materials, hydrogels with multiple shape memory effect have been studied to achieve shape programming [86–89,91]. In [87], a hydrogel actuator that can perform controlled sequential actuation through the combination of ionoprinting of iron and vanadium hinge lines with selective redox reactions was presented. A discussion on shape-morphing hydrogels is presented in [21,70,90].

Moreover, chemo-responsive materials generally possess a stiffness that can be tuned over various orders of magnitude by the stimulus, see, e.g., [106–111] and references therein. Similar observations hold for the Poisson's ratio [114] and electrical properties [126]. Examples of programmable friction and adhesion are discussed in [116,118].

Various materials have been also used to manufacture photonic structures whose properties can be programmed and controlled through shape changes induced by variations of pH [144,145], moisture [32, 145], solvent [91], ions [145], and glucose [146].

Indeed, it is worth noting that while certain physical stimuli can be applied to materials remotely without direct contact, chemical stimuli typically require direct interaction with the material to be effective. Moreover, inducing precise, small-scale, and localized changes within a material and creating spatio-temporal changes can be challenging [20]. However, advancements in material science and engineering are addressing these challenges. For example, research has shown that through the careful design and manipulation of materials at the micro- and nano-scale, it is possible to achieve controlled local volume changes [204]. Introducing chemical stimuli via physical stimuli may also circumvent these limitations. For example, photoacids can change the environmental pH upon light irradiation. Furthermore, techniques are being developed to visualize and track ion dynamics into battery materials, which could lead to better control over spatio-temporal changes within these materials [205]. Research need to be conducted along this direction to couple these promising solutions with programmability.

Multi-responsive materials. To achieve advanced programmable behaviors, the use of multi-responsive materials, i.e., responding to a variety of external stimuli, has been also adopted. Generally, the broad responsivity is programmed by combining different responsive moieties together in one material system, which brings increased material complexity, but also new perspectives.

Examples of shape-programmable materials include: light/temperature-responsive shape memory polymers [92], solvent/temperature/ Fe^{3+} concentration-responsive shape memory hydrogels (see [96] and references therein), hydrogels exhibiting shape memory behavior under multiple stimulation conditions including temperature variations and FeCl_3 and ascorbic acid glycerol–water solution at sub-zero temperatures [97], dual-programmable organo-hydrogels that are thermo- and Fe^{3+} concentration-responsive [95], low melting point materials with magnetic-driven and IR photo-thermal nanoparticles [100], and photo-humidity driven toner-coated papers with biaxially oriented polypropylene [101]. Bobnar et al. [93] used the temperature-induced hardening of main-chain liquid crystal elastomer (MC-LCE) to functionalize a conventional silicone rubber with thermally-driven shape memory capabilities. Moreover, an additional thermo-mechanically reversible response was imprinted into the composite by magnetically-aligning MC-LCE microparticles prior to curing the matrix. Lu et al. [99] developed a thermo- FeCl_3 concentration-UV light-responsive shape memory hydrogel containing short alkyl chains modified polyvinyl alcohol (PVA-C6) and polyacrylamide-co-polyacrylic acid [P(AAm-co-

Fig. 14. Examples of materials with programmable optical properties. (A) Display actuated by pressure given by a glass plate with convex letters “LSW”. Images show color changes induced by the convex letters superimposed with a gradient stress field. Adapted with permission from [142], copyright 2014, Springer Nature. (B) 4D printed programmable electro-active color-changing samples. A V-shaped CB/PLA nanocomposite material was printed into the TP/PLA composite. After the switching on the circuit, the V-shaped areas gradually changed color and became visible. Adapted with permission from [198], copyright 2021, Elsevier. (C) Exposure of a functionalized surface to varying concentrations of biotin leads to variation of the optical response (measured by OD_{450} absorbance). Biotin vs. optical signal curves for both the indirect (left) and direct (right) functionalized surface schemes. Adapted with permission from [199], copyright 2017, JoVe. (D) Printed metalattice pattern with encoded scanning powers at 25 °C. Transformed patterns at 50 °C, and the emerging of the Mona Lisa. Adapted with permission from [200] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). (E) Patterned thermo-chromic photonic film applied in the encrypted anti-counterfeiting, inspired by the dynamic camouflage in chameleons. Adapted with permission from [201], copyright 2022, John Wiley and Sons and from [202] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

AAc)]. The ion-responsive shape memory process of P(AAm-co-AAc) provides the pre-programmed morphological information and actuating force, while the thermo-responsive hydrophobic clusters of PVA-C6 are utilized as a molecular switch to control the deformed posture within the deformation process. The incorporation of the photo-thermal particle Fe_3O_4 allows to generate different configurations that can be encoded under the application of NIR light. Besides, the obtained morphological information can also be erased through immersion of the hydrogel in hot water, due to the disassociation of PVA-C6. Zhou et al. [94] adopted a dual shape-programming strategy to produce programmable structures made of polyacrylamide/gelatin and poly (acrylamide-co-methacrylic acid)/gelatin hydrogels. Particularly, supramolecular assembly was used as the first programming

to control the initial anisotropy of hydrogels, while shape memory as the second programming to generate temporary anisotropy. The final system is able to respond to thermal stimuli as well as to pH variations due to the existence of carboxylic acid groups. A shape memory hydrogel was prepared by mixing cysteamine grafted alginate and poly(vinyl alcohol) at room temperature in [98]. The material can switch between two different shapes in response to individual stimuli (Ca^{2+} , redox, or heat). Moreover, the shape memory can be further programmed to accomplish sequential quadruple shape memory when applying Ca^{2+} , redox, and heat stimuli sequentially. Lv et al. [102] integrated electrically-conductive liquid metals and shape-morphing liquid crystal networks to develop soft robots that can be electro- and photo-thermally actuated.

Further, in the case of multi-responsive materials the stiffness can be tuned upon changing different environmental conditions; see [110] and references therein. Yun et al. [112] dispersed hybrid fillers of Field's metal (FM) and spiked nickel (Ni) microparticles in a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) matrix, creating an electro-mechano responsive FM-filled hybrid elastomer exhibiting reversibly switchable stiffness and tunable electrical properties. In fact, FM fillers avoid the extremely low solidifying temperature, while Ni microparticles give high strain sensitivity and improve microstructural strength and mechanical stability. The material exhibits temperature-dependent electrical and mechanical properties. Yue et al. [206] reported the design of nucleic acid-based, constitutional dynamic network (CDN)-guided hydrogel materials. The adaptive, switchable, and reversible transitions of the CDNs across three different states lead to hydrogels exhibiting high, medium, and low stiffness. These properties were used to yield self-healing hydrogels, stimuli-controlled release of loads, and a switchable activation of enzyme cascades.

Similar observations hold for electrical and electromagnetic properties. Cai et al. [127] investigated the temperature- and strain-induced tunable electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding effectiveness (SE) obtained by introducing temperature-sensitive microspheres (TSM) into the mixture of polydimethylsiloxane/multi-walled carbon nanotube (PDMS/CNT), as shown in Fig. 15A.

A polyacrylamide-co-methyl acrylate/spiropyran (SP) hydrogel crosslinked by SP mechanophore demonstrated thermo-, photo-, and mechano-induced color changes [147]. Thanks to the combination of a fluorescent dye-labeled hairpin DNA with a photoresponsive molecule, Lin and coauthors [57] designed a programmable color-change biointerface that responds to UV light and DNA.

Other materials. Alternatives to stimuli-responsive materials include the development and use of programmable phase change materials, e.g., for latent heat storage applications as in greenhouses to support heating energy reduction or to reduce the risk of frost [207]. These materials are characterized by high enthalpies of melting and crystallization, in which they can change their state from solid to liquid and vice versa by releasing and storing thermal energy. Switchable phase change materials are also characterized by the ability to store their latent phase change enthalpy over a large number of cycles even below its crystallization temperature in a supercooled state [207,208]. Recently, Schonfeld et al. [208] proposed a self-regulating device for the repeated temperature-controlled release of heat from sodium acetate trihydrate used as switchable phase change material. The programmable release was made possible by exploiting the two-way shape memory effect of phase-segregated polyester urethanes. In fact, contact of the crystal nuclei with the switchable phase change material was established upon cooling to release thermal energy and inhibited upon heating to regenerate the system. A discussion on the use of phase change material behavior to add programmability or tunability to optical and photonics components by changing the refractive index of the material is available in [209].

Other materials, as liquid crystals, which combine liquid-like stimuli-responsiveness and crystal-like orientational ordering, silk proteins, luminescent materials, and metasurfaces have emerged as highly appealing soft materials for the dynamic control of light [210].

Finally, it is worth mentioning that recent research has also focused on the development of programmable photovoltaic materials [211]. Photovoltaic materials are semiconducting materials that can absorb light and generate electricity. They can be mainly classified into four categories [211]: (i) silicon-based solar cells; (ii) inorganic compounds-based solar cells; (iii) organic materials-based solar cells; (iv) perovskite solar cells. For a detailed discussion the reader is referred to, e.g., [211]. Bidirectional, colorful perovskite solar cells with high efficiency based on optical interference effects within the multilayer solar cell structure were presented in [212] for applications as power-generating surfaces, energy-efficient display systems, and self-powered

wearable electronics. Tunable reflective colors across the whole visible region were achieved by simply tuning the thickness of a transparent electrode of the solar cell. The reflective colors are produced by using a small proportion of the visible solar spectrum. Kim et al. [213] proposed to incorporate a color-tuning scheme into transparent photovoltaics to reach a high level of sustainability by harnessing energy from structures such as windows on buildings and vehicles. To this purpose, they proposed a method for this using a ZnO-based back reflection method. Other solutions relying on the coupling of photovoltaic materials with geometrical arrangements are discussed in Section 3.3.

3.1.2. Material property gradient

Programmable materials can be generated by using one single material whose properties change along the macroscopic dimensions of the material structure. Particularly, these varying properties enable the material structure to respond differently to applied external stimuli, thus giving the possibility to program the properties of the final material [29]. Such an approach is often referred to as "bulk material programming" [214]. It is worth underlying that material structures involving changes of the chemical composition, such as the introduction of multiple (different) materials, are discussed in the next section.

Table 3 contains some examples of works achieving programmable behavior through the use of these property gradients.

From the reported examples, it is clear that this strategy primarily focuses on shape-programming.

To this purpose, one approach consists in properly disposing properties' variations along the macroscopic dimensions of the structure. Current solutions include the generation of gradients due to variations of the cross-linking density [90,189,215–217] or ion distribution [90, 218,219] in the plane or along the thickness of the material structure as well as due to anisotropic distributions of the material [90,220,221]. Using 3D printing, these changes can be arranged more easily than with traditional manufacturing processes [29,189,214,217,221]. For instance, gradients in the crosslinking density can be generated by exploiting the process typical of VAT polymerization technologies. Recently, Bonetti et al. [222] have proposed a simple and promising approach toward programmability to 4D print solvent-triggered, gradient-based bilayers made of semi-crystalline crosslinked polymer networks via fused particle fabrication extrusion-based technique. Also, using 3D printing, material can be more easily distributed anisotropically. As an example, Fig. 16A shows the patterning of surfaces made of hydrogel containing poly(sodium acrylate) with ion inkjet printing [218]. Based on the patterning, it is possible to program the shape changes upon hydrogel swelling.

Scientists have also sought to modify the wettability of interfaces by creating wetting gradients or by constructing anisotropic physical patterns on solid surfaces to program the motion of liquids [24]. These ideas are based on the principle that droplets naturally migrate towards areas of greater wettability (see [24] and references therein). As an example, programmable diffusion of droplets can also be realized by modulating current intensity through local gradients [24,224]. Further, Luo et al. [169] used one-way shape memory polymers to achieve isotropic/anisotropic sliding and enable the switching of microstructures between random and ordered states upon temperature variations (Fig. 7B). These surfaces facilitate the reversible writing and erasing of linear structural motifs, endowing them with the capacity to reconfigure the trajectory of droplet movement. Moreover, the infusion of perfluoropolyethers into the shape memory polymer arrays makes feasible to precisely manage the initiation and cessation of droplet motion.

Surface chemical gradients can also be used to induce wetting gradients in liquid matter. This type of approach will be discussed in next section, since it assumes the use of different chemistries.

Another approach consists in strategically localizing the stimulus and/or employing a combination of different stimuli. As an example, laser can be used to induce localized stress relaxation for programming

Fig. 15. Examples of materials with programmable electromagnetic properties. (A) Temperature- and strain-induced tunable EMI SE obtained by introducing TSM into the mixture of PDMS/CNT. Adapted with permission from [127], copyright 2021, Elsevier. (B) Measured and simulated transmittances of frequency selective surface (FSS) kirigami specimens in their closed and fully open configurations. In inset (f), simulation of the switchable on-off FSS obtained by modifying the star pattern with the introduction of little metallic notches or tiny springs, as shown in the unit cell inset, which act as short circuits of the slots corresponding to the cuts defining the kirigami pattern in the closed configuration, while their presence has practically no effect when the FSS is stretched open. Adapted with permission from [55] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

stress gradients and thus shape changes, as demonstrated in [225]. Zhang et al. [226] proposed a strategy using the solution of a disulfide-containing diamine for patterned secondary crosslinking of an optical shape memory polymer network. The strategy enables welding, re-configuration, re-programming, and complex shape transformations of the thermo-photo-solvent-responsive material.

The programming approach based on material property gradients presents three main advantages if compared to multi-material structures, treated in the next section. Firstly, it circumvents the high shear stresses at the interface of two different materials, thereby eliminating the risk of delamination and/or interfacial sliding. Secondly, it avoids adhesion issues that may arise from the use of multiple materials. Thirdly, fabrication of multi-material structures often requires multiple fabrication steps, which could be reduced in the case of a single material. However, this programming approach is more difficult to control

and it poses greater challenges when attempting to realize sophisticated tunable shape changes.

3.1.3. Multiple materials

Programmable materials can be composed of two or more constituent materials, each with distinct properties. These varying properties enable the materials to respond differently to external stimuli, thus giving the possibility to program the behavior of the final material. Such a strategy has been also referred to as “patterning” [214] or “material tessellation” [29].

Table 4 contains some examples of works achieving programmable properties through the use of a multi-material approach.

This approach is particularly useful for programming the change from a two-dimensional to a three-dimensional shape [28]. In this context, bilayer approaches are the simplest method to induce folding

Fig. 16. Examples of materials with programmable shape. (A) Patterning hydrogel surfaces with ion inkjet printing. Adapted with permission from [218], copyright 2017, John Wiley and Sons. (B) 4D printed bi-material box. The bottom part of the box was printed with the polycaprolactone methacrylated (PCLMA)-only ink (“pure ink”) and the top lid was printed with the ink containing 40 wt% N-Vinylcaprolactam (NVCL) (“mixed ink”). Sequential shape changes due to the different recovery temperatures of the two inks. Adapted with permission from [223].

Table 3
Examples of programmable properties achieved using material property gradients.

Programmable property	Type of change	Examples
Shape	Cross-linking density gradients	[90,189,215–217,226] & refs therein
Shape	Ion distributions	[90,218,219] & refs therein
Shape	Anisotropic physical structures	[90,220,221] & refs therein
Shape	Localized stress relaxations	[225]
Motion	Wetting gradients	[24] & refs therein
Motion	Anisotropic physical structures	[24,169] & refs therein
Motion	Surface charge density gradients	[24,224] & refs therein

of a two-dimensional material structure [34]. This is due to the distinct properties of the two material layers. When a stimulus that alters volume is applied, it leads to differential stress. If one layer is highly rigid, the other layer may either wrinkle or crease. Conversely, if the layer is soft and pliable, it allows for the folding or bending of the entire structure. Although the structures resulting from folding differ from those arising from wrinkling and creasing, the fundamental mechanisms are interconnected. Furthermore, by increasing the number of layers, one can create structures with more complex, yet analogous, behaviors. This multi-layered approach allows for a greater variety of shape transformations, expanding the potential applications of programmable materials. Moreover, the resulting curvature can be estimated using or extending the Timoshenko theory for the bending of bimetal thermostats [227].

Beginning with this straightforward example, it becomes evident that a strategically-designed arrangement of materials within the structure is crucial for attaining a programmable behavior of the structure itself [19,29,228].

To this purpose, many works relied on the use of different stimuli-responsive materials to create shape-programmable multi-layer [229,230] or multi-material (see [16,21,198,223,229,231–236] and references therein) structures. As an example, Fig. 16B shows the sequential opening of a 3D printed box with two lids via direct heating. The sequential recovery of the two lids is associated to the different recovery kinetics of the two polycaprolactone methacrylated-based shape memory polymers composing the lids, that have different glass transition temperatures due to the different ratio of N-Vinylcaprolactam and featuring the one-way shape memory effect. Liu et al. [236] printed individually photo-sensitive resins with different glass transition temperatures. Then, the different components are assembled through interfacial welding in order to obtain a multi-material structure which can exhibit regionally-selective and multi-modal deformations.

The inclusion of more complex shapes, such as paths, fibers, sheets, and hinges, using materials with a different composition/behavior from

the rest of the structure, often helps not only in achieving a more complex programmable behavior, but also tunable and enhanced response times; see [16,231,233,237] and references therein. Yue et al. [238] introduced grayscale digital light processing 3D printing for fabricating shape-morphing hinge modules that can be cold-programmed. Different configurations can be encoded during 3D printing with the variable distribution and direction of the modular-designed hinges. The modules allow controllable independent morphing enabled by cold programming. The use of multiple materials within specific architectures, such as metamaterials and origami, is treated in Section 3.3. Moreover, we have not considered here materials with fillers or particles since they have been already discussed in Section 3.1.1.

Other programmable properties have been also achieved. Sharifi et al. [239] designed and fabricated an elastomeric pad made of polydimethylsiloxane, which is embedded with a spiral channel filled with a low melting point alloy (LMPA). Once the LMPA strip is melted upon Joule heating, the compliance of the composite structure increases and the friction between the composite surface and the opposing surface increases. Tunability can be achieved by varying geometrical parameters.

Structural colors programming can be achieved using multi-material and multi-layer systems, including the approach of reconfigurable liquid crystals, electrochromic and plasmonic modulation, mechanical stretching, and self-assembled colloidal microspheres [240]. Chen et al. [198] obtained an electro-responsive shape-changing and thermal shape-color dual-response material by means of multi-material double-nozzle fused deposition modeling 3D printing. The electric shape memory material was synthesized via carbon-black (CB) nanoparticles and PLA. The thermal shape-color dual response materials were synthesized via thermo-chromic pigments (TP) and PLA. By meticulously managing the printing process and the structure being printed, it was possible to precisely regulate the electrical heating region. This precise control is essential for realizing the programmability of the material.

Table 4
Examples of programmable properties achieved using multiple materials.

Programmable property	Type of materials' disposition	Examples
Shape	Multi-layer	[229,230]
Shape	Multi-material	[16,21,198,223,229,231–236,238] & refs therein
Shape	Multi-material with pre-stress	[241,243–246]
Adhesion & friction	Multi-material	[239]
Optical	Multi-material	[198,240] & refs therein
Optical	Multi-layer	[240] & refs therein
Motion	Surface chemical gradients	[24,170] & refs therein

Fig. 14B shows the so-obtained 4D printing programmable electroactive color-changing samples.

As anticipated in previous section, surface chemical gradients can be also used to induce wetting gradients and thus control liquid motion; see [24] and references therein. In fact, the distribution of concentration and composition of substances or functional groups can alter the hydrophilic/hydrophobic ratio on the surface as well as the surface free energy of the liquid. Fig. 7C shows an example of selective droplet transport within three independent zones on a pre-strained polydimethylsiloxane film [170]. The zones were characterized by three wettability gradients obtained using a template vapor deposition method. The mechano-switchable transport properties of these zones were then used for zonal activation (“on”) and deactivation (“off”) of transport.

It is important to recognize that the discussed examples depend on a uniform application of an external stimulus to induce and program shape changes. Nevertheless, it is possible to localize these changes to the surface or to particular parts of the structure through a non-uniform application of the stimulus, as treated in detail in Section 3.2. As an example, Zhang et al. [241] proposed shape-programmable bilayer structures by depositing an IR light-responsive shape memory polymer on a pre-strain layer using 4D printing. Recently, an approach, known as “direct 4D printing” [242], has exploited internal stresses generated during the printing process to induce a pre-programming of one-way shape memory polymer layers. In this way, after printing, structures composed of active materials (i.e., shape memory polymers) and passive materials (i.e., not responding to the stimulus) are able to change their shape after heating [243–246].

3.2. Stimulus

As already anticipated in previous sections, programmable behavior is attainable through a strategic application of the external stimulus (see the second box of Fig. 4). Both physical and chemical stimuli, along with mechanical loads, can be applied uniformly or non-uniformly across the material. In addition, there has been a successful utilization of biological stimuli to achieve desired responses.

In the following, we discuss all the approaches schematized in the second box in Fig. 4.

3.2.1. Physical and chemical stimuli

The application of either physical or chemical stimuli to responsive structures –previously outlined in Section 3.1– is often favored over mechanical loading due to its efficacy to achieve autonomous or self-programmable materials.

The uniform application of one or more stimuli to both single-material and multi-material structures is widely recognized in current literature research for its straightforwardness; some examples have been reported, e.g., in Figs. 5A, 9A, 9B, 11A, and 16B. Furthermore, uniform stimuli are often employed to trigger buckling mechanisms, enabling the transition between various instability modes or the fine-tuning of instability onset [29,247]. This facilitates the creation of programmable mechanisms, which will be elaborated upon in Section 3.3.

The non-uniform application of one or more stimuli create stress gradients either through the thickness or across the plane of the mate-

rial structure as well as can induce buckling mechanisms. This approach is particularly beneficial for shape-programming [29,247]. Within the spectrum of physical and chemical stimuli examined above, light stands out as a straightforward method for localized excitation [129,139]; some examples have been reported, e.g., in Figs. 5B and 14A. Regarding mechanical loads, the application of localized pre-strains is prevalent [34], especially in the context of the multi-material systems outlined in Section 3.1 (see Fig. 7C). Recently, Tian and Wang [248] fabricated a monolayer-based stretchable and mechanically-robust polycaprolactone/polydopamine elastomer. Combined with photo-induced stimulation, the anisotropic polymer chain relaxation of the pre-stretched film can generate asymmetric contractions and sequential, controllable out-of-plane bending actuations.

3.2.2. Biological stimuli

A quite recent way for programming material properties employs biological components, such as cells, micro-organisms, bacteria, or explanted whole-muscle tissues, as “bio-actuators” or “bio-hybrid actuators” [21,249,250]. In this sense, it differs from the approach based on materials responsive to bio-chemical stimuli reviewed in Section 3.1.

Table 5 contains some examples of works achieving programmable properties through the use of biological components as stimuli. Published works are mostly limited to shape-programming and many efforts still have to be done towards the realization of programmable materials. The stimulus is determined by the type of biological component used, that can vary from cells to tissues.

Bio-actuators that necessitate spontaneous contraction frequently utilize cardiomyocytes because they autonomously generate action potentials and persist in actuating as long as glucose is available as energy source [250]. These cardiac-derived muscle cells are also responsive to electro-stimulation, which enhances control and programmability. This capability allows for the actuator to be activated or deactivated as needed, with the ability to adjust the frequency and intensity of the actuation.

In their research, Miotto et al. [165] showcased the use of human corneal stromal cells as adjustable bio-actuators for crafting shape-changing tissues. They employed self-assembled $C_{16}G_3RGDS$ peptide amphiphiles (PA) to regulate the cell-driven contraction within the matrix. Specifically, the inhibitory effect of PA in gel contraction was investigated by culturing cell-encapsulated, compressed PA/collagen gels for 7 days in presence of fetal bovine serum (+FBS) and serum-free medium (SFM) conditions (see Fig. 5C).

Various bodily tissues utilize elastin, a naturally thermo-responsive fibrous protein, which provides mechanical compliance and elasticity. Consequently, elastin-like polypeptides have been employed to create programmable biomaterials that boast enhanced mechanical and thermo-responsive characteristics for biomedical applications [251]. The thermo-responsive feature of these polypeptides permits the fine-tuning of material properties, including shape transformation capabilities.

Heyde et al. [199] developed a programmable biotin-streptavidin interface that is responsive to biotin produced by synthetically-engineered *Escherichia coli*. Fig. 14C demonstrates how it is possible to control the optical response of the interface (monitored by quantifying

Table 5
Examples of programmable properties achieved using biological components.

Programmable property	Type of biological component	Examples
Shape	Human corneal stromal cells	[165]
Shape	Cardiomyocytes	[250] & refs therein
Shape	Elastin-like polypeptide	[251] & refs therein
Shape	Explanted whole-muscle tissues	[250] & refs therein
Shape	Insect self-contractile tissues	[250] & refs therein
Shape	Engineered skeletal muscle tissues	[250] & refs therein
Optical	Escherichia coli	[199]

the optical density at 450 nm (OD_{450}) by exposing the functionalized surface to varying concentrations of biotin.

A significant challenge with cellular-based bio-actuators is the requirement to sustain the cells in a medium enriched with glucose, salts, and other nutrients, while also preventing metabolic wastes from accumulating to toxic levels. Moreover, external control and reversibility of these bio-actuators can be challenging. Accordingly, recent research has concentrated on modulating contraction. An innovative method involves optogenetics, which uses microbial agents or viruses to implant light-responsive proteins in living cells, thereby enabling control over various cellular processes through an externally applied light [250].

Finally, the living components typically cannot be resized but must be utilized in their natural form. This restriction means that bio-actuators are not universally applicable but rather tailored for specific applications, such as targeted drug delivery or lab-on-a-chip technologies for microscale motile cells and swimming robots or fluidic pumps for whole-muscle tissues. These examples demonstrate the application-specific nature of these actuation systems, as further discussed in [250]. To scale up bio-hybrid systems, larger biological actuation units are essential. This requirement has spurred research into using tissues as actuators, from skeletal muscle to insect self-contractile tissues; see [250] for a review.

3.3. Geometrical arrangements

Programmability can be achieved through the geometric structuring of materials, as illustrated in the third box of Fig. 4. This approach is further advanced by the rapid evolution of diverse manufacturing techniques which expand the design freedom [25]. Building on this, Cai et al. [252] introduced the term “mechanomaterials” to describe materials with programmable properties at various scales. These properties are achieved by applying mechanical forces and designing geometries during fabrication, or by tailoring post-fabrication behaviors under mechanical forces.

In the subsequent sections, we explore the strategies outlined in the third box of Fig. 4. In particular, we focus on three main approaches, respectively, based on engineered architectures, origami/kirigami designs, and bioinspired designs.

3.3.1. Architectures

Within this class, we consider all the materials whose behavior is programmable thanks to the engineering of their geometry through periodic or aperiodic spatial arrangements (or tessellation of units) or assembling of building blocks, according to pre-defined requirements.

Table 6 contains some examples of works achieving programmable properties through the use of rationally-designed architectures. The latter include lattice materials, metamaterials, tensegrity structures, functionally-graded materials (FGMs), and building blocks.

Lattice materials. Lattice materials refer to cellular materials with periodic arrangements of unit cells in two or three dimensions [253]. Thanks to their porosity and well-defined unit cell geometries, they are suitable candidates to achieve lightweight structures with enhanced mechanical properties. Generally, lattice designs, coupled with buckling-induced mechanisms or made of stimuli-responsive materials or multi-material designs, are employed to achieve programmable

behavior [254]. Accordingly, lattice materials with tunable deformation modes [255], stiffness [255–258], and Poisson’s ratio [255] were proposed. Despite these contributions, the design of lattice materials with enhanced programmable behavior and multi-functionalities is still a challenging topic [253].

Metamaterials. Metamaterials consist of periodically/aperiodically arranged units and exhibit unusual properties that could not be easily found in natural materials or in the bulk counterpart of the constituent. The family of metamaterials includes optical, acoustic, electromagnetic, and mechanical metamaterials across multiple length scales, with the unit cell and feature size ranging from millimeters to nanometers [259–262]. It should be noted that lattice materials and origami/kirigami designs are often categorized within the class of metamaterials [263]. However, in this context, we aim to differentiate between the three approaches.

Programmability of metamaterials is usually achieved by means of buckling-induced mechanisms, stimuli-responsive materials, multi-material designs, or applied mechanical loads. Accordingly, metamaterials with tunable deformation modes [17,200,264–268], stiffness [185,254,269,270], Poisson’s ratio [166,254,267,271–273], friction [274], damping and energy absorption [46,185,269,275–278], thermal properties [178,271,279,280], electrical properties [197], electromagnetic properties [267,281], acoustic properties [52,200,266,273,280,282–284], and optical properties [32,58,200,285,286] were proposed. Fig. 6B presents topology and shape optimized 3D printed unit cells for a programmable range of Poisson’s ratio values under mechanical loading. Fig. 12B shows a programmable damping effect in a metamaterial unit cell by varying the applied mechanical loading. Fig. 9B shows the thermal tunability, in terms of effective conductance, G_{eff} , of shape memory metamaterials (ϵ is the strain, F is the mechanical compressive force, Q''_{in} is the incoming heat flux, G_i is the effective conductance, and t is time). Fig. 13B shows the capacitance change in an auxetic deformation shape memory recovery experiment. Zhou and coauthors [287] showed that the wave propagation in a finitely pre-deformed elastic half-space overlain by a thin coating layer (or surface film) is affected by the surface film and pre-deformation. Recently, Morvaridi et al. [288] demonstrated the possibility of achieving tunable topologically-protected edge modes through the application of uniaxial prestrain in an auxetic metamaterial. Wang and colleagues [268] integrated programmable photonic capabilities with composite elastomeric materials, resulting in the creation of opto-mechanical actuators. These actuators exhibit adjustable and precise movements when exposed to light. The manipulation of photonic bandgaps in a spatial manner enables the targeted actuation of the elastomer when it is illuminated. Fig. 14D shows how to use a linearly responsive, transparent poly(NIPAM-co-HEMA-co-AM) hydrogel for information encryption. Upon thermal heating, the printed metalattice composed of a wide range of reconfigurable patterns showed the image of the Mona Lisa painting.

Tensegrity structures. Tensegrity structures, which consist of discontinuous struts and continuous cables, achieve structural stability only when self-stress is applied. Without it, they can collapse into a compact form, preserving their topological integrity but not their geometric shape. This design eliminates the need for the intricate joints found

in traditional truss- or origami-based deployable structures, as the struts are joined by the cables' flexibility. Shape-programmable tensegrity structures made of one-way shape memory polymers [289] and silicone-based elastomers mixed with iron oxide magnetic microparticles [290] were proposed. Fig. 17A demonstrates the programmed deployment of layered tensegrity structures using one-way shape memory polymers with different glass transition temperatures for the struts.

Functionally-graded materials. FGMs are characterized by their gradually varying composition and nano-/micro-structural patterns, which can be either chemical (not covered in this section) or structural gradients [252]. It is important to note that FGMs with structural gradients demonstrate mechanical properties that surpass those of materials with uniform or random structures. These properties include overcoming the usual compromises between strength and ductility, exhibiting remarkable strain hardening, and offering increased resistance to wear, corrosion, fracture, and fatigue [252].

For instance, Somam and colleagues [294] created both single-layered and multi-layered scaffolds from a polyethylene glycol-derived biomaterial. These scaffolds, functioning as FGMs, consist of pores with unique geometries and deformation mechanisms. They are engineered to demonstrate variable Poisson's ratios, capable of displaying either auxetic properties (negative Poisson's ratio) or conventional properties (positive Poisson's ratio), depending on the lateral or vertical configuration.

Recently, Duan et al. [295] presented a versatile and competitive approach for miniaturized bandgap-tunable perovskite spectrometer platforms and artificial vision systems. Specifically, a programmable mixed electrohydrodynamic printing technique is presented to realize the one-step direct-printing of arbitrary spatially-graded perovskite micro/nanopatterns for the first time.

Building blocks. The idea behind such an approach is to create independent building blocks that can autonomously come together (or separate) to form larger (or smaller) programmable structures [296].

According to Campbell et al. [14], the potential of this approach can be better understood by referencing to DNA-driven biological systems. In fact, biological life is composed of 22 building blocks – amino acids – that arrange themselves in various permutations to give rise to a myriad of proteins and, eventually, life forms.

Accordingly, following the discussion by Campbell and coauthors [13], a useful concept for contemplating programmable materials is the “voxel” or “volumetric pixel”. Similar to the way DNA and amino acids function, a pixel is a building block of an image, while a voxel represents a pixel in three-dimensional space — that is, a volumetric pixel. Therefore, in the realm of programmable matter, a voxel serves as the fundamental unit from which complex materials and structures can be constructed. For example, a voxel might be a synthetic particle of variable size, composed of materials ranging from silicon and ceramics to plastics and titanium, or it could be engineered to function as a subsystem — for instance, an energy-storage device, an actuator, a sensor, a conductor, an insulator, a protective shell, an antenna, or even a microcomputer. Voxels could be assembled and collectively programmed to alter shape or function, forming diverse objects. Once the object is no longer required, it can be disassembled, rendering the voxels available to create other tools or components.

Topological interlocking employs a design strategy that can be grouped within this approach. In fact, uniquely shaped elements, or blocks, are organized to ensure the entire structure is secured by an overarching peripheral constraint [297]. Simultaneously, each element is held in position by kinematic constraints derived from its shape and the arrangement relative to adjacent elements. This concept involves dividing a solid material into uniform, interlocking units that connect in three dimensions, creating a cohesive assembly. Consequently, the geometry of each unit restricts its movement, endowing the collective structure with the ability to bear loads and other performances without additional connectors or binders [252,298]. To preserve the integrity

Fig. 17. Examples of materials with programmable shape. (A) Deployment of tensegrity structures made of different shape-memory polymers for the struts. Reused with permission from [289] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). (B) Inverse design that defines the mesostructure of flat-fabricated shells that morph into the target geometries. Shells are composed of inhomogeneous tessellations of unit cells with an interior pre-stretched membrane. Simulation and experiments are compared at time steps in water. Adapted with permission from [291] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). (C) Kirigami sheets at different levels of applied deformation. Reused with permission from [292], copyright 2019, John Wiley and Sons. (D) Sequentially-deployed smart robotic hand under UV light (395 nm wavelength) for 20 min and in 60°C water. Reused with permission from [293], copyright 2019, Elsevier.

of the structure as a whole, a global constraint –such as a surrounding frame, corner fasteners, or tensioned cables– is essential.

Benyahia et al. [299,300] addressed multi-material 4D printing from the perspective of interlocking blocks assembly. They proposed a computational approach that converts a multi-material 4D object with a computed digital materials' distribution into suitable interlocking blocks. The latter can be printed separately using single material additive manufacturing and then assembled to achieve the targeted shape change. Later, Benyahia et al. [301] compared structures printed in one single step with interlocking ones. Experimental tests and numerical simulations demonstrated that interlocking structures exhibit relevant mechanical performance, while enhancing better actuation response than multi-material structures within a single print.

Guo et al. [302] enabled the transformation of 15 representative materials with different sizes, shapes, compositions, and functionalities (i.e., polymeric particles, metal oxide particles and wires, noble metal nanoparticles, upconversion nanoparticles, coordination polymer nanowires, nanosheets, nanocubes, and cells) into building blocks for the construction of complex three-dimensional superstructures, including core–satellite, hollow, hierarchically organized supraparticles, and macroscopic hybrid materials. To this end, they employed polyphenol-based surface functionalization, consisting of a particle surface functionalization with polyphenol moieties followed by particle assembly directed by interfacial molecular interactions and interparticle locking of the functionalized particles using metal ions.

Liu et al. [167] began with a Wohllhart polyhedron module, characterized by a single degree of freedom, and investigated its topological transformations across various motion trajectories via kinematic bifurcations. This exploration was marked by the ability to tune mechanical properties such as Poisson's ratio, chirality, and stiffness (see Fig. 6C). Moreover, these modules were assembled into three-dimensional metamaterials, leveraging their adaptability to independently tailor Poisson's ratios across orthogonal planes. This enables a broad spectrum of customization, ranging from negative to positive, and even zero Poisson's ratios.

Recently, Duque [303] applied this approach to triply periodic polyhedra to develop arbitrarily large unit cells of tunable, defined size.

Guseinov et al. [291] demonstrated a method for encoding temporal shape evolution in architected shells that assume complex shapes and doubly-curved geometries (Fig. 17B). The shells are non-periodic tessellations of pre-stressed contractile unit cells that soften in water at rates prescribed locally by mesostructure geometry.

Jiao [304] presented novel hierarchical metastructures composed of postbuckled elements which have programmable tensile and compressive moduli, zero Poisson's ratio, and recovery from large deformation.

Starting from the potential of mixing disconnected building blocks in a fluidic medium, Djellouli et al. [305] realized a so-called “metafluid” with programmable compressibility, optical behavior, and viscosity by mixing highly deformable spherical capsules into an incompressible fluid.

Other architectures. Other types of architectures, not belonging to previous classes, have also been proposed.

As an example, Zhang and coauthors [54] have developed a metagel that incorporates patterned channels within a tough hydrogel matrix, endowing it with tunable acoustic properties across a wide range of frequencies. By channeling different mediums such as air, water, or liquid metal, the metagel's acoustic transmission can be precisely modulated across various mediums and frequency bands. Additionally, the volume ratio of the channels is a key factor in fine-tuning the acoustic characteristics.

Furthermore, a novel heterophasic ionogel has been engineered in [306]. This ionogel merges microstructural alignment for modifiable stiffness with shape memory inclusions that maintain stiffness, making it suitable for adaptive pressure sensors. The unique feature of this material is its programmable pressure-deformation response, allowing

for customizable pressure-resistance profiles, detection thresholds, and high-resolution sensing at elevated pressures.

The design in [307] incorporates mechanisms for capturing energy on demand, facilitated by the interaction of buckled, slender components.

Researchers have also worked on the design of substrates using arrays of surface microstructures to program the motion of liquid matter (see [24] and references therein).

3.3.2. Origami and kirigami design

Origami and kirigami designs are popular candidates in the design of materials with programmable properties [10,309]. If rationally-designed and possibly coupled with other key ingredients such as stimuli-responsive constituent materials or applied stimuli, this approach enables programmability.

Table 7 contains some examples of works achieving programmable properties through the use of origami and kirigami designs.

Origami is an ancient art and science of paper folding. Typically, an origami-based material is created by stacking a series of foldable origami patterns, each of which is formed by the repetitive tessellation of origami units [310].

Tunable shape [10,175,238,309,311–315], stiffness [175,309,311,316], Poisson's ratio [168,312], and thermal properties [47,48] have been achieved. As an example, Overvelde et al. [175] proposed a modular origami-like design that switch between different states and stiffnesses by simply applying a compressive load (see Fig. 8B). Fig. 6D shows the tuning of the Poisson's ratio ν_{WL} of Miura-ori and Egg-box patterns by varying the folding angle Ψ . Many works have also leveraged on the use of active materials to develop autonomous, self shape-programmable origami structures; see [317] for a comprehensive review. Typical examples of active materials comprise shape memory alloy [10,35,318], stimuli-responsive hydrogels or polymers [319], and one-way shape memory polymers [316]. In [320], the combination of origami geometry with duct acoustics has enabled the development of a modular origami silencer. This device can significantly adjust and program sound attenuation levels due to its ability to undergo shape reconfiguration induced by folding. Perforated Miura-ori phononic structures with different design parameters demonstrated extensive bandgap tunability during deployments and folds in [321]. Their potential applications, such as programmable acoustic waveguides, were also demonstrated. A novel design of origami phononic structures with tunable waveguiding features was studied in [322]. The structure is formed by attaching cylindrical inclusions onto an origami sheet; then, the folding of the underlying origami sheet can alter the periodicity of the inclusions. Thus, the origami structure exhibits bandgap features and has the potential to direct wave energy through a path of defects (also known as a waveguide) created in the lattice of inclusions. Since the spectral content transmitted through the waveguide is dependent on the periodicity surrounding it, the folding-induced lattice transformation in such origami structures can lead to an adaptation in waveguide frequency. In fact, in origami structures that can transform between different Bravais-lattice types, for example, between a square and a hexagonal lattice, the waveguide frequency can be significantly tuned. Marras et al. [323] demonstrate an approach to engineer complex and reversible motion of nanoscale DNA origami machine elements. A micro-origami technique was developed to program three-dimensional metal halide perovskite microarchitectures toward a new type of microcavity laser in [324]. The technique has great potential for optoelectronic and photonic applications ranging from photovoltaics to laser devices.

It is worth remarking that origami structures have finite thickness, and formalizing the use of origami rules for computer modeling remains challenging. This is due to the zero-thickness assumption and the omission of mechanical properties in current origami models.

Kirigami is the Japanese art of paper cutting. It involves cutting paper to create intricate designs that can expand and contract, allowing for out-of-plane deformations.

Table 6
Examples of programmable behaviors achieved using rationally-designed architectures.

Programmable properties	Type of architecture	Examples
Shape	Lattices	[255] & refs therein
Shape	Metamaterials	[17,200,264–268]
Shape	Tensegrity structures	[289,290]
Shape	Topological interlocking	[299–301]
Shape	Interparticle locking	[302]
Shape	Wohllhart polyhedron modules	[167]
Shape	Triply periodic polyhedra	[303]
Shape	Jigsaw-inspired modules	[90]
Shape	Pre-stressed blocks	[291]
Stiffness	Lattices	[255–258]
Stiffness	Metamaterials	[185,254,269,270] & refs therein
Stiffness	Wohllhart polyhedron modules	[167]
Stiffness	Jigsaw-inspired modules	[90]
Stiffness	Postbuckled elements	[304]
Stiffness	Metafluid	[305]
Poisson's ratio	Lattice materials	[255]
Poisson's ratio	Metamaterials	[166,254,267,271–273] & refs therein
Poisson's ratio	Functionally-graded materials	[294]
Poisson's ratio	Wohllhart polyhedron modules	[167]
Adhesion & friction	Metamaterials	[274]
Damping	Metamaterials	[46,185,269,275–278] & refs therein
Thermal expansion coefficient	Metamaterials	[271,279,280]
Thermal conductivity	Metamaterials	[178]
Electrical	Metamaterials	[197]
Acoustic	Metamaterials	[52,200,266,280,282–284,287,288] & refs therein
Electromagnetic	Metamaterials	[267,281,308] & refs therein
Optical	Metamaterials	[32,58,200,285,286] & refs therein
Optical	Metafluid	[305]
Motion	Surface microstructures	[24] & refs therein

Tunable shape [292,325–327] (Fig. 17C), stiffness [328], and Poisson's ratio [329–331] were achieved. Two examples were presented by Grima et al. [330,331] who achieved tunable auxetic behavior. The Poisson's ratio, ranging between 0 and -1, was independent of the facets' size but dependent on their rotation angles. Hwang et al. [184] showed that tunable and anisotropic adhesion responses can be developed through kirigami-inspired adhesives made of an adhesive layer and encapsulation layer of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) separated by an inextensible polyethylene terephthalate (PET) strip (Fig. 11B). A kirigami-inspired ring-like microstructure with shape memory alloy sheets/patches was proposed in [179] as a new building brick for designing materials with coded thermal expansion properties that support targeted isotropic and anisotropic deformations upon thermal changes (Fig. 9C). Khosravi and colleagues [181] conducted research on the control of elastic wave propagation bandgaps within kirigami structures that exhibit periodicity and multiple stable states. They achieved this by arranging the mechanical components of the kirigami in a specific sequence. Each component within the stretched kirigami material is capable of switching between two stable configurations, which are distinct in their external geometries-referred to as the "(0)" and "(1)" states (Fig. 10B). By strategically sequencing these (0) and (1) states, it is possible to alter the fundamental periodic structure of the material. This alteration, in turn, allows for the tuning of the frequencies at which phononic bandgaps occur, effectively programming the material's ability to control the propagation of elastic waves. An on-chip and electromechanically reconfigurable nano-kirigami with optical functionalities was manufactured in [332]. Yang et al. [55] have applied the principles of kirigami to create multistable mechanical metasurfaces. These surfaces are capable of deforming into various shapes and locking into different configurations, which allows them to serve as reconfigurable electromagnetic structures. This approach offers a cost-effective solution with a wide range of design possibilities. The key to their functionality lies in the unit cells of the metasurface, which are designed based on kinematic principles and are coated with

a metallic layer. As these cells rotate relative to one another, they can alter their resonant electromagnetic properties. Fig. 15B shows the measured and simulated transmittances $|T|$ of these kirigami designs in their closed and fully open configurations to polarized incident waves. A switchable metasurface absorber based on a rotary transformable kirigami configuration was numerically and experimentally characterized in [56].

To the best of author's knowledge, the use of origami and kirigami designs for programming liquid motion is still an unexplored field.

3.3.3. Bioinspired design

Nature uses various mechanisms to program actions and responses of biological organisms such as solar tracking in sunflowers, shriveling of the surface of fruits, peacock and butterfly colors, fast motions in plants, growth of the skin and organs during metamorphosis cycle, and folding in pine cones [14]. These mechanisms include, e.g., the development of cellular and extracellular layers, swelling, inhomogeneous contraction or expansion of elements, different effects of dehydration on different layers, and activation of snap-through instabilities [333]. Li et al. [334] reviewed the actuation strategies associated to plant movements, including pressurized cellular structures, osmotic actuation, anisotropic hygroscopic materials, and bistable systems, and showed that different combinations of these strategies can lead to motions with different deformation characteristics and response speeds. It is clear that these programmable natural mechanisms originate from a proper spatial arrangement of the structural elements at different length scales and/or from their differential responses to stimuli [29]. Understanding and replicating such natural principles may provide new routes to develop materials with programmable capabilities [228].

Table 8 contains some examples of works achieving programmable properties through the use of bioinspired designs.

Inspired by actomyosin network, Kidambi et al. [335] proposed a modular, architected material system that leverages spatial constraints

Table 7
Examples of programmable properties achieved using origami and kirigami designs.

Programmable property	Type of design	Examples
Shape	Origami	[10,175,238,309,311–315]
Shape	Kirigami	[292,325–327]
Stiffness	Origami	[175,309,311,316]
Stiffness	Kirigami	[328]
Poisson's ratio	Origami	[168,312]
Poisson's ratio	Kirigami	[329–331] & refs therein
Adhesion & friction	Kirigami	[184]
Thermal expansion coefficient	Origami	[47,48]
Thermal expansion coefficient	Kirigami	[179]
Acoustic	Origami	[320–322]
Acoustic	Kirigami	[181]
Electromagnetic	Kirigami	[55,56]
Optical	Kirigami	[332]
Motion	Origami	[323]

to generate multi-stable topologies and yield large adaptability of material mechanical properties. The research by Schmied et al. [336] presents an example of biomimicry, drawing inspiration from the *Dionaea muscipula* leaf, commonly known as the Venus fly trap. They developed programmable shells capable of morphing through a snap-through mechanism, which allows for rapid shape changes. These shells are composed of a composite material consisting of epoxy and stiff anisotropic alumina micro-platelets. The orientation of these micro-platelets was carefully controlled through magnetic alignment, enabling the precise tuning of pre-strain and stiffness anisotropy within the material. Inspired by biological dynamic materials capable of bending, twisting, and spiraling using site-specific aligned cellulose microfibrils orientations, Ren et al. [293] proposed an approach integrating bioinspired fiber architectures and varying 3D printing parameters into shape memory polymers to achieve tunable permanent shape and shape memory properties. This kind of technology enables the creation of adaptable robotic hands that can perform a wide range of tasks with precision and varying levels of force, similar to a human hand (Fig. 17D). The design allows for tunable deformation rates, degrees, and forces in each finger, which is achieved through the strategic orientation of fibers within the fingers.

The three-segment continuum robot, inspired by the elephant trunk's ability to regulate local stiffness, indeed utilizes tensegrity structures (Fig. 8C) [36]. The robot's stiffness can be programmed thanks to a low melting point alloy, which allows for a significant change in Young's modulus –from 1.79 MPa to 271.62 MPa– when the temperature is altered. This property enables the robot to adapt its stiffness characteristics dynamically, similar to how an elephant trunk operates, providing a versatile tool for various applications such as search and rescue, medical assistance, and complex environmental interactions.

Wang et al. [337] reviewed materials and devices with switchable adhesion, that take inspiration from different types of living organisms. In particular, switchable adhesives, modulated by external stimuli and divided into mechanically-based, liquid-mediated, physically-actuated, and chemically-enhanced, are discussed.

Li et al. [338] utilized fused filament fabrication 4D printing to create flat structures that can transform into biomimetic dome structures through thermal stimulation. This process is inspired by the dome-shaped structures found in nature, which are known for their impact resistance. The research highlights that it is possible to control the structural patterns of the flat precursors by programming the printing process parameters. These structures not only mimic the geometry but also the functional aspects of natural domes, such as energy absorption. Furthermore, the mechanical properties, particularly the compressive characteristics, vary with the design patterns.

Inspired by self-shaping systems capable of autonomous transformation through significant hygroscopic expansion or mismatch in the coefficients of thermal expansion of constituent materials, a surface with programmed thermal emissivity behavior is achieved in [180]. This is due to the anisotropic nature of the material's microstructure. The material exhibits a two-way memory effect, and its morphing mechanism is activated by the mismatch in the coefficient of thermal expansion across the multi-layer structure, along with the resultant stresses within the layered material (Fig. 9D).

Dielectric elastomer actuator-based unimorphs that actively bend in one direction, mimicking the blooming motion of flower petals, were used in [182] to create tunable acoustic absorbers capable of adapting to fluctuations in dominant noise frequency (Fig. 10C).

Yang et al. [92] have developed a bioinspired EMI shielding coating material that demonstrates EMI shielding performance, with an effectiveness of approximately 100 dB. This material has broad applicability across multiple applications. Drawing inspiration from the adhesion mechanism of mussels, the researchers modulated the interactions among the coating's components (cellulose nanofiber, carbon nanotubes, and polydopamine). This modulation allows the coating to adhere to a variety of substrates through different coating methods such as brush, spray, and dip coating. The coating provides comprehensive shielding and Joule heating properties. Crucially, it retains high shielding performance even when subjected to atomic oxygen, UV light, and rapid thermal shock, demonstrating significant potential for practical applications in extreme conditions, particularly in space exploration.

Inspired by the dynamic camouflage of chameleons and cephalopods, a programmable thermochromic patterned photonic film was developed for encrypted anti-counterfeiting in [201]. The film is constructed by infiltrating thermo-responsive poly(oligo ethylene glycol acrylate) (POEGA) copolymers in SiO₂-coated ZnS photonic crystals. The thermal range is identified by the lower critical solution temperature of filled copolymers, which is tunable by controlling the ratios of different monomers. Accordingly, the pattern is hidden either when the temperature is higher than 55 °C or lower than 5 °C; when the temperature matches the decoding temperature (equal to 20 °C), the different areas display the preset colors (Fig. 14E).

Inspired by the unique microstructure of plant stomata, Sun et al. [339] presented a surface with programmable wettability arrays for droplets manipulation and motion. The substrate film of this surface is constructed by using a coaxial capillary microfluidics to emulsify and pack graphene oxide (GO) hybrid N-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM) hydrogel solution into silica nanoparticles-dispersed ethoxylated trimethylolpropane triacrylate (ETPTA) phase. Because of the distribution of the silica nanoparticles on the ETPTA interface, the outer surface of the film could achieve favorable hydrophobic property under selective fluorosilane decoration. Due to the photo-thermal energy

Table 8
Examples of programmable properties achieved using bioinspired designs.

Programmable property	Type of design	Examples
Shape	Actomyosin network	[335]
Shape	Venus fly trap	[336]
Shape	Cellulose microfibers	[293]
Stiffness	Elephant trunk	[36]
Adhesion & friction	Various natural systems and animals	[337] & refs therein
Damping	Natural dome-shaped structures	[338]
Thermal expansion coefficient	Self-shaping systems	[180]
Acoustic properties	Petals	[182]
Electromagnetic properties	Mussels	[92]
Optical properties	Chameleons	[201]
Motion	Plant stomata	[339]
Motion	Skin of springtails and gecko feet	[340]
Motion	Nepenthes peristome	[171]

conversion properties of GO, encapsulated hydrophilic hydrogel arrays can contract into their cavities upon NIR irradiation, revealing their hydrophobic surfaces. This grants the composite film a remotely switchable surface for droplet adhesion. Leveraging this property, the authors achieved controlled droplet movement along programmable wettability pathways and effective droplet transfer for printing, integrating a mask that is challenging to accomplish with current methods. In [340], the researchers took inspiration from the unique skin of springtails and the adhesive capabilities of gecko feet to create programmable liquid adhesion on 3D printed microstructures with doubly re-entrant arrays. By strategically arranging these arrays, they were able to achieve three distinct types of Cassie adhesion states, i.e., residue-free, tunable, and absolute adhesion. Additionally, they engineered various array configurations to precisely control the movement and manipulation of both macro and micro liquid droplets. These innovations have potential applications in the precise transport of liquid droplets, concentration of liquids, creation of minuscule droplets, and formation of intricate micro-patterns. Drawing inspiration from the natural *Nepenthes* peristome, researchers have developed a novel surface with anisotropic wettability characterized by periodically aligned and overlapping arch-shaped microcavities (Fig. 7D) [171]. This surface was created using ferrofluid assemblies as dynamic templates, allowing for precise control over the strength and orientation of the magnetic field H during the fabrication process. Consequently, the size and inclination angle of the ferrofluid droplet templates can be customized, resulting in a polymer replica surface that closely mimics the natural peristome structure. The anisotropic wettability surface facilitates autonomous, fast, and continuous unidirectional water transport. Moreover, it can be shaped into various forms to direct water flow along predetermined curved paths. Significantly, this surface has been utilized to create novel pump-free microfluidic devices capable of conducting multiphase flow reactions, presenting a cost-effective and portable solution for lab-on-a-chip applications.

4. Applications

The extraordinary potential of programmable materials could be extensively leveraged across various fields, potentially enabling numerous innovative technologies. In fact, these materials can enhance the performance and simplify the design and manufacturing of engineered systems.

In the following we review and discuss the main application fields.

4.1. Biomedical applications

Programmable materials have great potential in minimally-invasive surgery, since their shape can be programmed for deployment purposes and/or their mechanical properties can adapt to the patient's needs or

to interact with biological tissues. Moreover, programmable materials may lead to functional robotic systems at the milli- and submilli-meter scale to be employed for surgical operations.

As an example, a stiffness-tunable soft device that combines a silicone body with a thermoplastic resin structure was proposed in [341] to enhance dexterity and adaptability by varying the temperature of the resin. This makes it a promising tool for performing complex tasks in narrow and delicate spaces, such as in medical scenarios, by serving as channel for delivering surgical instruments. Additionally, the actuator features three uniformly arranged pipelines for actuation by air and can be expanded with additional functional chambers for endoscopy, illumination, water injection, and other purposes. Fig. 18A shows a simulated clinical experiment using the developed instrument. Runciman et al. [342] developed a deployable, cable-driven robot designed to enhance the surgical capabilities of flexible endoscopes while minimizing their impact. This robot can be easily customized and rapidly produced at a low cost. It features a low-profile, inflatable support structure shaped like a hollow hexagonal prism. The robot can wrap around the flexible endoscope, and upon reaching the target site, it can expand to achieve a 73.16% increase in volume, thereby increasing its radial stiffness. A sheath enveloping the variable stiffness structure houses a series of force transmission cables. These cables connect to two independent tubular end-effectors, which allow standard flexible endoscopic instruments to pass through and be secured. The instruments' pose can be controlled using a straightforward control scheme that adjusts the length of each cable, manipulated by haptic controllers held by the user.

Magnetic-responsive soft devices with patterns of embedded, programmable domains have received significant attention in medicine, e.g., for cargo delivery, tumor ablation, ulcer therapies, and wound healing [343–345]. A review and discussion is available in [346].

Further interesting medical applications are programmable wearable exoskeletons for patient rehabilitation [347]. However, further efforts have to be made along this direction to couple programmable behavior with advanced functionalities.

4.2. Pharmaceutical and tissue engineering applications

The early concept of programmable materials has been introduced in drug delivery systems to ensure encapsulation and release of drugs in a programmed way via stimuli-responsive materials [28,253]. Also, drug delivery systems can be engineered to undergo sequential shape changes when a stimulus is applied for deployment or movement purposes.

At present, programmable polymeric containers have been developed at different scales (from millimeters to nanometers), with research efforts now focusing on creating even smaller systems [19,29,350].

Fig. 18. Examples of programmable materials employed in: (A) medical field. Simulated clinical experiment on a mannequin with laser ablation and surgical forceps grasping. Adapted with permission from [341], copyright 2023, Springer Nature; (B) pharmaceutical field. Switching between two states of swollen and shrunken microcapsules by NIR laser on and off. Adapted with permission from [348], copyright 2021, John Wiley and Sons; (C) soft actuators and robotics field. Applications of a droplet-driven micro-surfboard in traversing holes and transporting cargos to the target positions. Adapted with permission from [349], copyright 2022, Elsevier.

Choi et al. [348] engineered micro-capsules with a hydrogel membrane that exhibits a temperature-tunable permeation cut-off threshold. These micro-capsules demonstrate temperature-dependent variations in both radius and membrane thickness. The permeation cut-off threshold can be also reversibly modulated through temperature control, as the swelling degree diminishes with increased temperature. This feature facilitates selective molecular encapsulation and the programmed release of encapsulated substances by temperature adjustment. Additionally, the micro-capsules were made photo-responsive by incorporating photo-thermal polydopamine nanoparticles, enabling the control of the swelling extent via NIR irradiation (quantified by the normalized radius $R(t)/R(0)$ in Fig. 18B).

Moreover, programmable systems offer a high degree of customization, paving the way for personalized medical treatments [351]. Programmable materials can be engineered for biological purposes, i.e., designed to interact with biological entities and adjust to the evolving nature of diseases. As an example, they could be modified in response to disease-specific and/or environmental triggers, such as changes in pH, redox state, the presence of molecules, or the expression of certain proteins. Battistella and colleagues [352] have reviewed programmable soft materials that respond to disease-related stimuli. These materials undergo dynamic changes, including alterations in shape and size, mobility, and the ability to assemble or disassemble. Such materials have been utilized in treatments for cancer as well as for other conditions like myocardial infarction and diabetes mellitus.

Various researches have also demonstrated that material design, cellular microenvironment, tissue dynamics, and architecture provide meaningful information in cellular culture platforms [249]. In fact, the interaction between cells and the surrounding matrix has been found to be of great significance in many biological processes such as embryogenesis, tumorigenesis, and angiogenesis. Accordingly, one important application of shape-programmed materials may be the fabrication of three-dimensional dynamic cell-culture substrates or scaffolds to model specific cellular environments, giving a complete picture of the spatio-temporal chemical and mechanical information found in native tissue [353].

Zhang and co-workers [354] discussed recent advances in microfluidic platforms for programming cell-based living materials, including individual cells, cell-laden fibers, cell sheets, organoids, and organs in a high-throughput and efficient manner for diverse applications, such as cell therapy, tissue engineering, disease modeling, and drug screening. Ivanisevic and co-workers [355] discussed the concepts of inorganic substrate/microorganism biointerfaces serving as smart materials with desired responses to external conditions.

Liquid programming also shows broad application prospects in targeted cargo delivery and biomedical diagnostics [24,28]. In particular, droplet-based microfluidic manipulations can be applied to a variety of research fields from fundamental biochemical analyses to clinical and point-of-care diagnostics recently. As an example, multi-stage programmable bidirectional pumping was implemented on a

microfluidic platform, according to a newly established droplet manipulation principle, in [356] to illustrate its potential use for automated bio-microfluidic and point-of-care diagnostic applications.

4.3. Actuators and robotics

Programmable materials provide great advantages for realizing reconfigurable actuators and robots that can further adapt to environmental conditions, fragile objects, or people [28].

Programmability is generally achieved using stimuli-responsive materials. Among them, electro-responsive materials are the preferred choice since they can be easily integrated within robotic systems [357]. As an example, Yun et al. [112] demonstrated a self-triggered variable stiffness compliance compensator for robotic manipulators, with 10 times improved compensation capabilities than the best commercial products, by using electro-mechano responsive Field's metal-filled hybrid elastomers. Yun et al. [112] also designed a highly compact self-recovering resettable current-limiting fuse with a response 10 times faster than state-of-the-art resettable fuses. Using magneto-responsive materials, Lum et al. [77] created a jellyfish-like robot, a spermatozoid-like undulating swimmer, and an artificial cilium that could mimic the complex beating patterns of its biological counterpart.

As an potential alternative, mechanical or pneumatic actuation is widely exploited. Bell et al. [358] presented a modular, soft, bistable, one degree-of freedom dome actuator platform that is capable of complex gaits through mechanical programming, driven by simple periodic fluid input. With a modular, re-configurable design, the end effectors of these bi-stable dome actuators can be quickly modified for use on a variety of surfaces for specific applications.

Moreover, programmability may be achieved by exploiting mechanical metamaterials; see [359] for a detailed review and discussion on metamaterials for soft robotics.

Among them, auxetic metamaterials allow to design surfaces that conform well to complex curved shapes. This is particularly relevant when interacting bodies or objects with specific geometries. As an example, Berwind et al. [17] presented a mechanical metamaterial with strain-dependent solid–solid phase changes resultant from hierarchically-structured mechanisms built into an auxetic unit cell.

Metamaterials based on slender beam elements are widely used due to their easy manufacturing [360]. Moreover, buckling of beams enables large deformations at small forces, that is suitable for artificial muscles. Further, elastic beams that snap between two stable configurations, can be exploited to store and release elastic strain energy, as demonstrated by the temperature-responsive untethered soft robot proposed in [60].

Origami and kirigami designs have been also explored for programmable morphing in robotic applications. However, conventional origami designs difficulty carry mechanical loads. Accordingly, inspired by the programmable folding of the earwig wing, a bistable origami combined with load-bearing capacity and fast-morphing capabilities through multi-material 3D printing of rigid plates connected by soft stretchable joints in [361]. In [362], the Miura-Ori design was used to create a robotic hand. Kirigami structures were developed to enhance the crawling capability of soft actuators by mimicking the stretchability, friction anisotropy, and active anchorage of snake skins [359].

Knitted and woven fabrics have also attracted designers because of their potential for programming flexibility, strength, and shape change by tweaking the arrangements of yarn [265]. Artificial muscles made of textile actuators were fabricated by knitting and weaving cellulose yarns dyed with an electro-responsive coating, whereas morphing three-dimensional objects were made by knitting hybrid fibers containing one-way shape memory alloy wires [363]. Despite their advantages, knitting approaches for manufacture of reinforced metamaterials often require more complex processing and manufacturing steps.

Mabed et al. [364] proposed an original flexible distributed algorithm allowing to reorganize a set of modular micro-robot into a desired target shape.

It is worth noting that soft robotic and actuator systems require programmable materials that can withstand large deformations (around 50% strain) without breaking and fatigue failure. This still represents an open issue in current literature.

Moreover, programmability becomes fundamental for the control of the motion of robots. To this purpose, various researches have been dedicated in finding new strategies for program robots' motion and movements using, e.g., stimuli-responsive materials or external systems [60,365]. Recently, Paramanick et al. [59] presented a robotic system displaying a variety of active dynamics. It propels itself using the differential drive mechanism. Moreover, the robot houses hardware components like multiple IR and light intensity sensors which help it in detecting environmental factors like obstacles and ambient light and provide spatio-temporal control over its motion.

Liquid programming shows broad application prospects for developing self-propelled liquid microrobots [24]. In fact, conventional propulsion often requires special chemicals or external energy inputs, limiting its practical application due to environmental pollution and energy waste. In [349] a novel droplet-driven micro-surfboard (DDMS) was manufactured via femtosecond laser micro/nano fabrication (Fig. 18C). The DDMS is composed of a superhydrophobic sheet with superhydrophilic wedgy grooves. The droplet is put on the superhydrophilic wedgy grooves to enter the water and form a jet, which further facilitates the directional motion of the DDMS. Also, an actuator based on three superhydrophilic wedgy grooves is designed to achieve programmable motion by adding droplets to the three channels. Finally, an actuator with circular water storage area and a symmetrical vane-like rotating device with two superhydrophilic channels were developed, realizing long-distance and rotational motions.

4.4. Flexible and wearable electronics

Programmable materials exhibit variable stiffness and flexibility under different conditions, making them well-suited for designed scenarios and mechanical deformations without incurring damage in flexible and wearable electronics [366].

As an example, a wearable glove based on stretchable capacitive sensors with tunable sensitivity enabled by liquid metal microstructure is reported in [367]. A review and discussion on how programmable materials are capable of enhancing the performance of flexible sensors is provided in [368].

Such a field still needs research efforts to exploit the potential of programmable materials.

4.5. Aeronautical and aerospace applications

Programmable materials hold promise for aeronautical and aerospace applications due to their ability to provide a programmed assembly, which is highly beneficial for remote applications that face volume constraints during shipping and re-assembling stages. Thus, shape-programmable deployable systems have been proposed, such as those based on origami theory [238,314], also at the meter scale [315] (Fig. 19A), thermo-responsive kirigami designs [327], and thermo-responsive tensegrity structures [289].

Additionally, novel aerospace structures with embedded multi-phase materials with tunable stiffness and damping parameters were proposed in [369]. The proposed materials exploit the thermal loads generated in high-speed flights to tune the stiffness and damping parameters, and thus, enable adaptive aeroelastic stability. Cramer and colleagues [370] developed a programmable material system designed for large-scale, lightweight, and adaptable aeroelastic structures. Utilizing a modular, lattice-based, ultralightmaterial, it achieves the flexibility characteristic of an elastomer, with a stiffness of 2.6 MPa,

while maintaining a mass density akin to an aerogel at $\left(5.6 \frac{\text{mg}}{\text{cm}^3}\right)$. This approach, coupled with a building block manufacturing and configuration method, facilitates the swift creation of novel adaptive structures and mechanisms. Its design, featuring programmable anisotropic properties, enhances both the elastic and overall shape changes under external forces, making it ideal for optimized fluid–structure interactions. Tunable acoustic metamaterials becomes fundamental for noise reduction which is still an issue [371].

However, it has to be taken into account that in these application fields materials need to satisfy a series of requisites due to the harsh environment, including, e.g., very high/low temperatures or gamma-ray irradiation exposure as well as appropriate mechanical properties [347, 372, 373]. Research has still to be done in this direction, especially regarding stimuli-responsive soft materials.

4.6. Civil engineering, architecture, and mechanical applications

Programming the shape is very advantageous for architectural purposes, in particular for realizing smart facades. The project HygroSkin – Meteorosensitive Pavilion was first shown in the exhibition ArchiLab 2013 [376]. HygroSkin is a climate-responsive architecture, in which the paper thin wooden flaps autonomously open and close in response to the surrounding humidity without requiring any kind of mechanical or electronic control [376, 377].

Moreover, programmable materials find applications for noise reduction and controlled air ventilation. An origami window ensuring a balance between noise reduction and air ventilation in response to different working conditions was proposed in [374] (Fig. 19B).

Damping programming becomes important for engineering structures and mechanical components and systems. As an example, NASA Langley Research Center developed a self-tuning compact damper to reduce vibration occurring at a fixed frequency [378]. Researchers at Fraunhofer Institutes [185] have developed programmable damping systems based on metamaterial unit cells. Recently, Zeng et al. [379] proposed an approach to develop 4D printed metamaterials based on shape memory polymers with programmable load plateaus to be used, e.g., for vibration damping in automotive seats and for vibration suppression in satellite platforms.

4.7. Optical and electromagnetic applications

Materials with programmable optical properties attracted significant attention because of their potential applications as functional optical components in fields such as optical communication, display technology, computing, anti-counterfeiting, and biology.

External stimuli can be used to induce structural changes in certain materials and thus modulate their optical performance. As an example, Li et al. [380] proposed a thermally induced optical beam-power splitter concept based on a shape memory polystyrene film with programmable micropatterns. The smooth film exhibits excellent transparency with a transmittance of 95% in the visible spectrum and optical stability during a continuous heating process up to 90°. By patterning double sided shape memory polystyrene film into erasable and switchable micro-groove gratings, the transmission light switches from one designed light divided directions and beam-power distribution to another because of the optical diffraction effect of the shape changing micro gratings during the whole thermal activated recovery process.

Also, geometrical arrangements can be employed to program the materials. As an example, a novel origami-based acoustic metamaterial with tunable and broad bandwidth sound-eliminating capacities was developed in [53] by incorporating the accordion origami into Helmholtz resonators as the side cavity.

Materials with programmable electromagnetic properties can be employed in tunable electromagnetic wave devices (e.g., absorbers, filters, phase shifters, microwave switches), frequency-, polarization-, or phase-reconfigurable antennas, and dynamic adaptive radar absorbing structures [381].

4.8. Personalized objects, textiles, and furniture

Programmable materials are promising solution for realizing personalized objects, textiles, or furniture, since they can adapt to specific needs or to the surrounding environment.

An example along this line was proposed in [382], where 4D printed shoes were fully personalized for a single user. The shoes were made of a commercial styrenic block copolymer thermoplastic elastomer (known as FilaFlex) and their geometry designed to change and adapt to the user's movements and changes. The designers emphasized key design considerations, including aesthetics, comfort, durability, balance, and temperature regulation [377].

A review on programmable fabrics is available in [383]. Singal et al. [375] proposed knitting to realize a therapeutic glove by interchanging knits and purls to program the fabric's local elastic response (Fig. 19C). In this way the prototype is able to direct the stiff elastic response to support the wrist joint in cases of repetitive stress injury, while enabling natural motion for the rest of the hand. Recently, Loke and coauthors [384] created the first fiber with digital capabilities, able to sense, store and analyze body temperature data, and infer activity after being incorporated into a shirt. A scalable preform-to-fiber approach is used to produce tens of meters of flexible fiber containing hundreds of interspersed, digital temperature sensors, and memory devices.

Another example is the so-called programmable table, that is a furniture manufactured with the 4D technology by MIT's Self-Assembly Lab and Wood-Skin S.r.l., in order to solve volume problems in shipping and storage [385]. It has a flat structure and the ability to reach its three-dimensional form by taking advantage of an embedded pre-stressed textile, without the need for human inputs, to self-transform in precise and predictable ways when it is removed from its packaging [377]. Once in-place this furniture may be reconfigured into other shapes or flattened again to reduce the volume for storage.

Shape-shifting mobile devices (denoted as Morphees) were proposed in [386]. The devices are flexible and capable of self-actuation and adaptation of their shapes to the context of use thanks to the use of shape changing materials (dielectric electro active polymers and shape memory alloys). For example, upon launching a game, the mobile device transforms into a shape reminiscent of a console by bending two opposite edges, allowing for a more comfortable two-handed grip.

5. Conclusions and perspectives

This paper has introduced readers to the world of programmable materials, covering the relevant state-of-the-art, recent progress, and ongoing challenges.

Although significant advancements have been made in the field of programmable materials, numerous opportunities remain in terms of material development, design and optimization methodologies, and technology exploitation leading to final market products.

Current limitations and future perspectives can be discussed by categorizing them into seven macro-areas, as follows.

1. Base materials. Today stimuli-responsive polymers, hydrogels, and metals represent the most employed solution to achieve programmability thanks to the numerous advantages discussed in Section 3.1.

However, many materials (e.g., shape memory) still experience irreversible changes when subjected to an external stimulus. Meanwhile, materials capable of reversible responses are confined to a limited spectrum of stimuli. These may not be suitable for certain applications since they may require enduring large temperature variations or operate within a liquid medium, where control over pH or ionic concentration is necessary. Thus, new opportunities to develop materials capable of reversible property changes are needed, together with investigations on their cyclic behavior or reusability.

Additionally, current limitations, such as the restricted range of attainable moduli, diminished robustness to failure, difficult real-time control, and slow response times, hinder the commercialization of

Fig. 19. Examples of programmable materials employed in: (A) aerospace. A tent-like design can be created by merging one layer of a Design I with another one of a Design IV. The fabricated meter-scale inflatable shelter can be inflated from a compact state to a fully deployed state. Owing to multistability, the door can be opened, making the internal space accessible. Adapted with permission from [315], copyright 2021, Springer Nature; (B) civil engineering and architecture. Room with origami silencing window. Adapted with permission from [374], copyright 2023, Elsevier; (C) personalized objects and furniture. Therapeutic glove prototype uses all four types of fabrics to generate anisotropic elastic response to the motion of the hand. Adapted with permission from [375] under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

materials. These challenges may be surmounted by incorporating ad-hoc fillers or reinforcements into the material, employing ad-hoc design principles, or integrating sensors.

Furthermore, the range of functionalities and properties that can be achieved readily and cost-effectively through current chemistries is often limited. This includes features such as biocompatibility, biodegradability, optical transparency, self-healing, and chemical inertness. For instance, the development of self-regulating hydrogel-based systems that respond not only to a specific enzyme but also exhibit programmable reactions to varying enzyme concentrations would be advantageous. This is particularly relevant since enzyme expression levels differ among various diseases and even at different stages of the same disease. Additionally, present research indicates that polymeric

materials typically show irreversible responses following enzymatic activity. The ability to reverse these changes would enable the on-demand release of therapeutic agents [387]. Specifically, it would allow for the interactive adjustment of drug dosage and release rates, tailored to the enzyme expression levels - a feature that would be extremely beneficial for long-term treatments. Also, the development of eco-friendly and recycled programmable materials will be an important future direction for their integration in sustainable applications [388]. A discussion on programmable biological materials and biopolymer-based shape-memory materials is provided in [350].

2. Stimuli. The most popular stimulus is thermal actuation due to its ease of implementation. However, other stimuli are also desired based

on the field of application. Various stimuli, such as ultrasound, still require further research efforts to exploit their huge potential.

Furthermore, power and energy sources play a crucial role in the actuation of programmable materials. The need for varying electric/magnetic fields or hydraulic/pneumatic actuation systems diminishes the appeal and practicality of using these materials in real-world applications. There is a need to devise innovative strategies for energy generation. Exploring wireless actuation methods, such as batteries, radio-frequency, photovoltaic power supplies, or energy harvesting technologies, presents a viable solution.

3. Geometrical arrangements. Structural organization is a critical aspect in the design of programmable materials, as relying solely on the properties of constituent materials is typically insufficient to elicit complex behaviors. However, this complexity can complicate the design process. For example, the adhesion between materials must be examined for long-term durability. Strategies ensuring the disassembly and reconfiguration of building blocks for reuse are necessary. Additionally, the actuation associated with numerous folding strategies often fails to produce substantial forces, thereby limiting their practicality.

4. Fabrication. While this paper does not delve into the fabrication strategies employed, it is evident from the literature that most studies utilize standard techniques such as molding, or more advanced and recent technologies such as 3D and 4D printing.

There is a need to develop advanced and innovative strategies that simplify the fabrication process of programmable materials without compromising fidelity, as well as to create cost-effective programmable material systems suitable for both small and large-scale production. Although 4D printing offers a promising avenue for the single-step manufacturing of stimuli-responsive materials, considerable work remains for various material classes and for nano- and micro-scale fabrication. Hybrid multi-material technologies, as those proposed in [389,390], has high potential in this field. Consequently, the preparation of materials for manufacturing through 4D printing also requires enhancement.

5. Control strategies. Despite efforts to control and program material changes, there is still much work to be done. Solutions that enhance the control of shape changes are essential for achieving sequential or programmed responses, which is necessary for creating more complex geometries and sophisticated applications. Folding rates could be optimized, along with the precision of folding dynamics typical of origami-based materials. Strategies such as snap-buckling instabilities could enable faster responses compared to the typically slower mechanisms that depend, e.g., on polymer shrinkage or gel swelling. Moreover, most processes often require substantial energy inputs. To this end, the integration of efficient and controllable electronics, or capabilities akin to electronics, should be considered.

6. Modeling. Advancements in modeling and numerical algorithms are essential to guide the optimal design of programmable material transformations.

Designers require software that can simulate these transformations and convert their designs into instructions comprehensible to 3D printers. In pursuit of this objective, Tibbits's team collaborated with the design software company Autodesk to create Project "Cyborg". This project facilitates the simulation and optimization of the dynamics of 4D printed objects.

Bioinspiration and artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms are increasingly becoming powerful tools for navigating the extensive design space and material chemistries.

The construction of a comprehensive library of designs will allow for the identification and assembly of functional modules into architectures. Such developments will empower machines to not only morph and interact safely with their environment but also to execute logical operations, perceive, and adapt, even within unstructured settings.

7. Applications. Currently, most applications of programmable materials are at a laboratory scale.

Programmability represents a novel approach to liquid control and offers extensive research opportunities for integrating liquids with smart systems. However, research on programmable droplets remains predominantly within the laboratory setting, confronting numerous challenges related to controllability and multi-functionality.

Finding a solution for realizing large-scale applications and mass production in the industry remains an urgent challenge. Additionally, the establishment of standards, such as those produced by ISO, and intellectual property rights are necessary to significantly influence the market. Programmable materials may complicate the traceability of product origins for consumers and lawyers. It is conceivable that one could replicate objects with identical form and function, or even direct the objects to self-assemble.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Giulia Scalet: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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